

Ruprecht Karl University of Heidelberg
Institute of Computer Science
Fundamentals of Intelligent Planning

Bachelor's Thesis

LLMs for textual plan space explanation in PlanPilot

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Submission date: 18.05.2026

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LLMs for textual plan space explanation in PlanPilot

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Abstract

Planning is a crucial component of processes in many domains, including production lines, general problem-solving, optimization, or many others. However, planning as a research field often remains difficult to understand and inaccessible to non-experts. To address this issue, the PlanningCopilot is introduced. It combines the PlanPilot planning system with a large language model (LLM) to bridge the gap between complex planning systems and users of varying levels of expertise. The goal is to allow for an easier usage of PlanPilot and, in doing so, making planning as a whole more accessible to everyone.

To evaluate whether this objective was achieved, a user study was conducted and analyzed. The results show that the PlanningCopilot successfully enables users to explore the plan and facet spaces, review the plans, and adapt them to their individual needs. Test participants reported a significantly improved user experience and considerably easier usability compared to PlanPilot. Furthermore, the integration of an LLM also enables new functionalities such as swap detection.

Zusammenfassung

Planung ist in vielen Bereichen ein entscheidender Bestandteil von Prozessen, sei es in Produktionslinien, der allgemeinen Problemlösung, der Optimierung und Vielem mehr. Dennoch ist Planung als Forschungsbereich für Laien oft schwer greifbar und wenig zugänglich. Dies soll sich durch den PlanningCopilot verändern. Dieser verbindet das Planungssystem PlanPilot mit einem Large Language Model (LLM). Dadurch soll eine Brücke geschaffen werden, die unabhängig vom Wissensstand die Nutzung des PlanPilot-Systems ermöglicht und Planung zugänglicher macht.

Ob dies gelungen ist, wird zusätzlich durch die Auswertung einer durchgeführten Nutzerumfrage geprüft. Dabei zeigt der PlanningCopilot, dass er Nutzern erfolgreich ermöglicht, in die Plan- und Facettenräume einzutauchen, Pläne einzusehen und eben jene den eigenen Bedürfnissen anzupassen. Die Tester attestieren dem neuen System eine deutliche Verbesserung der Nutzererfahrung und eine erheblich einfachere Bedienung im Vergleich zu PlanPilot. Besonders hervorzuheben sind auch die Funktionen, die durch das LLM erst möglich werden, beispielsweise eine "Swap"-Erkennung.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Planning helps to solve key issues in industry and science, but non-experts might struggle with understanding due to the rather complex nature of how the optimal solutions are calculated and presented. In recent years, large language models (LLMs) have revolutionized many areas of modern life by offering an easy way to obtain explanations in natural language regardless of the topic. Combining these two fields can substantially lower the bar of entry into planning.

Letting LLMs help explain planning problems and their solutions, if used correctly, can open a lot of possibilities for the optimization of production lines, transport routes, or logistics in, for example, warehouses (e.g., in the Beluga problem). This could make it possible to work with planning systems without needing specific knowledge or a lot of time to understand the details.

With that in mind, the goal of this thesis is to connect the LLM ChatGPT to the PlanPilot command line tool. PlanPilot allows users to traverse the plan space and enables plan modification through the activation and deactivation of facets¹. But PlanPilot still needs the user to know the necessary terminal-commands for controlling the program, and also have the ability to understand the output's details on their own. Here, the LLM comes into play, as it is able to respond in plain text and can handle all kinds of questions. The user can issue demands in plain text and the copilot translates these into commands for PlanPilot. However, the LLM should never solve a problem on its own due to a high error rate [2]. To achieve a more flawless system here, the LLM only takes the data from the output of PlanPilot and then answers the user questions while referencing these. So, none of the solving is actually done by the LLM.

¹A facet is a decision point in the plan space representing the inclusion or exclusion of an operator, through this defining planning alternatives and enabling reasoning about different plans and outcomes. [1]

1.2 Research Objective

The goal is to create a copilot called "PlanningCopilot". This is a large language model that controls the command line tool PlanPilot for the user by translating their input into commands, and then is able to explain the resulting output. The PlanningCopilot should make it possible for non-experts of planning and PlanPilot to successfully explore the plan and facet spaces. All of this is intended to be achievable using plain language, rather than through specific commands as necessary in PlanPilot.

1.3 Overview

To begin with, the necessary background information about planning will be defined. Then an introduction to the PlanPilot program and its components is provided. Subsequently, the new PlanningCopilot and its features are explained. Two demonstration walkthroughs follow to provide a deeper understanding. Afterwards, the new program is evaluated by presenting the results of a conducted survey. Finally, possible future improvements are stated and a conclusion is drawn.

2 Background

The Background chapter provides all the necessary information for a deep understanding of the topic. Here, the basics of planning, Answer Set Programming, and facet reasoning are explained. Also, a short introduction to the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) and the blocks world domain is given.

2.1 Classical Planning

Classical planning [3] describes the problem of finding a finite sequence of actions that transforms a given initial state into a state satisfying a goal condition. A classical planning task can be represented as the following tuple:

$$\Pi = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{G} \rangle$$

Here \mathcal{A} is a finite set of propositional state variables, \mathcal{O} is a finite set of actions, \mathcal{I} is the initial state and \mathcal{G} is the goal condition.

A (partial) state s is defined as a total (partial) mapping from the set of state variables in \mathcal{A} to truth values, formally given by $s : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. The partial state p is satisfied by a state s if all literals specified by p hold in s , i.e., $p^{-1}(0) \subseteq s^{-1}(0)$ and $p^{-1}(1) \subseteq s^{-1}(1)$. This is denoted by $s \models p$.

Each action $o \in \mathcal{O}$ is represented as a tuple of partial states: $o = \langle pre_o, eff_o \rangle$. Where pre_o is the precondition of the action and eff_o is its effect. The Action $o \in \mathcal{O}$ is feasible in the state s , if s meets the precondition: $s \models pre_o$. $s[[o]]$ is the application of the action o to the state s , which then leads to a successor state s' . This successor is determined by the effect eff_o , for every variable a , if $a \in dom(eff_o)$ then $s'(a) = eff_o(a)$, if not then $s'(a) = s(a)$. Any state where $s_* \models \mathcal{G}$ is called a goal state.

A plan is a sequence of actions $\pi = \langle o_0, \dots, o_{n-1} \rangle$ such that the actions are applicable in this order, resulting in a state sequence s_0, \dots, s_n starting from $s_0 = \mathcal{I}$, where $s_{i+1} = s_i[[o_i]]$ for $i \in [n-1]$ ends in a goal state: $s_n \models \mathcal{G}$.

$|\pi|$ is the length of a plan π and π is optimal if there is no other plan with a length shorter than π , formally, $\neg \exists \pi' \in Plan(\Pi)$ with $|\pi'| < |\pi|$.

Furthermore, the set of all valid plans is described by $Plans(\Pi)$, while plans of at most length ℓ are denoted by $Plans_\ell(\Pi)$. In the literature, this is sometimes referred to as plan space.

2.2 Answer Set Programming

Answer Set Programming [3], or ASP for short, is a declarative programming paradigm used to solve combinatorial and reasoning problems, such as planning, scheduling, or configuration tasks. Instead of describing how to solve a problem algorithmically, ASP describes the logical rules and constraints that characterize solutions.

An ASP program consists of a set of logical rules. A typical rule r , for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ and distinct propositional atoms: $a, b_1, \dots, b_m, c_1, \dots, c_n$, has the following form:

$$a \leftarrow b_1, \dots, b_m, \sim c_1, \dots, \sim c_n$$

This represents: when all b_1, \dots, b_m are true and there are no signs that any of c_1, \dots, c_n are true, then a must also be true.

ASP also supports constraints, written as:

$$\leftarrow b_1, \dots, b_m, \sim c_1, \dots, \sim c_n$$

A constraint does not derive new information. Instead, it eliminates interpretations where all b_i are true and all c_i are false.

A rule is divided into three components:

- $H_r := \{a\}$, which contains the derived atom for the rules, or $H_r := \emptyset$ for the constraints
- $B_r^+ := \{b_1, \dots, b_m\}$, which contains the atoms that must hold
- $B_r^- := \{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$, which contains the atoms that must not hold

Then a program P is a finite set of such rules. $M \subseteq vars(P)$ defines an interpretation M , a rule r is satisfied by M if:

- $(H_r \cup B_r^-) \cap M \neq \emptyset$
- Or $B_r^+ \not\subseteq M$

An interpretation M that satisfies every rule $r \in P$ in the program is called a model of the program P .

The Gelfond–Lifschitz reduct is used to determine whether an interpretation is an answer set. Given a program P and an interpretation M , the reduct P^M is formally defined as:

$$P^M := \{H_r \leftarrow B_r^+ \mid B_r^- \cap M = \emptyset\}$$

An interpretation M is an answer set of P if M is a model of the original program P , and there is no interpretation $N \subsetneq M$, where N is a model of the reduct P^M .

2.3 Facet Reasoning

Facet reasoning [1] is a qualitative form of reasoning in the solution space of a planning task that goes beyond simply asking whether a plan exists or how many plans there are. It identifies the operator-level structure of the plan space by comparing operators that occur in some valid plans (brave operators), with those that occur in all valid plans (cautious operators).

The brave operator is defined by $\mathcal{BO}_\ell(\Pi) := \cup_{\pi \in \text{Plans}_\ell(\Pi)} \nabla(\pi)$ and the cautious operator by $\mathcal{CO}_\ell(\Pi) := \cap_{\pi \in \text{Plans}_\ell(\Pi)} \nabla(\pi)$ for a planning task $\Pi = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{G} \rangle$, an operator $o \in \mathcal{O}$, and an integer ℓ .

$\nabla(\cdot)$ denotes the conversion of sequences into sets, since the sole objective is for an operator to occur at any given time step.

Through this, it is possible to calculate the inclusive facets with the formula $\mathcal{F}_\ell^+(\Pi) := \mathcal{BO}_\ell(\Pi) \setminus \mathcal{CO}_\ell(\Pi)$ and also denote $\mathcal{F}_\ell^- := \{\neg o \mid o \in \mathcal{F}_\ell^+(\Pi)\}$ as the excluding facets (operators not part of a plan). In addition, $\mathcal{F}_\ell(\Pi) := \mathcal{F}_\ell^+(\Pi) \cup \mathcal{F}_\ell^-(\Pi)$ describes the set of all existing facets.

A facet p , where $p \in \{o, \neg o\}$, is directly associated with uncertainty. This comes from the fact that the operator o may or may not appear in a plan, since it is possible to include or exclude it. $\Pi[p]$ describes that a facet p is enforced, which means that p has to be present in a plan. This reduces uncertainty and allows the significance of an operator to be measured.

The significance $\mathbb{S}_\ell(\Pi, o)$ for an operator $o \in \mathcal{O}$ and a task $\Pi = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{G} \rangle$ is denoted by:

$$\mathbb{S}_\ell(\Pi, o) := \frac{|\mathcal{F}_\ell(\Pi)| - |\mathcal{F}_\ell(\Pi[o])|}{|\mathcal{F}_\ell(\Pi)|}$$

Facet reasoning, in general, is closely related to answer set programming and planning under uncertainty. Since a logic program can have multiple answer sets, different plans or states may be possible. Facets capture this variation by expressing whether an operator or state condition holds in some, all, or none of the answer sets. Thus, facet reasoning provides a compact way to represent and reason about uncertainty across multiple possible solutions.

2.4 Blocks World Planning Domain

In the field of planning, there are many different planning problems, such as the Beluga problem from the Beluga AI Challenge by Tuples or the rovers problem [4]. However, in the context of this thesis, blocks world [5] was used to test the program and also in the examples that follow later.

The blocks world planning domain consists of blocks, each labeled with different letters. At the start of the problem they are placed on a table, and to reach the goal state these blocks need to be stacked into one or more towers in a predefined order. Blocks that have one or multiple blocks on top cannot be moved, and only one block may be moved at a time.

The following four actions are possible: put-down (placing a block from the hand onto the table), pick-up (picking up a block from the table into the hand), stack (stacking the block from the hand on top of another block), and unstack (picking up a block into the hand that is currently stacked on top another block but itself has no block on top). With these actions, the blocks are then moved to transition from the initial state to the goal state.

2.5 Planning Domain Definition Language

The Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) was first introduced by Drew McDermont [3] and is used to describe planning problems in a human-readable format. For PlanPilot to solve a problem, it needs to have the problem and its domain defined in PDDL in two separate files.

```
1 (define (problem BLOCKS-5-0)
2   (:domain BLOCKS)
3   (:objects B E A C D )
4   (:INIT (CLEAR D) (CLEAR C) (ONTABLE D) (ONTABLE A) (ON C E) (ON E B) (ON B A)
5     (HANDEEMPTY))
6   (:goal (AND (ON A E) (ON E B) (ON B D) (ON D C)))
7 )
```

Code 2.5.1: Example of an instance file

In the example, the contents of the "probBLOCKS-5-0.pddl"², a file for a blocks world task are shown. Therein, the different blocks are stated under objects. Thus, five blocks "A", "B", "C", "D", and "E" are part of the problem. The initial state as well as the goal state are also declared. For example, D is initially declared as "ONTABLE", so at the start it is placed directly on the table. Also relevant is "CLEAR D", this indicates that no block is stacked on D. Under ":goal" the exact sequence in which the blocks need to be stacked, in order to complete the task successfully, is defined.

```
1 ...
2 (:action put-down
3   :parameters (?x)
4   :precondition (holding ?x)
5   :effect
6   (and (not (holding ?x))
7     (clear ?x)
8     (handempty)
9     (ontable ?x)))
10 (:action stack
11   :parameters (?x ?y)
12   :precondition (and (holding ?x) (clear ?y))
13   :effect
14   (and (not (holding ?x))
15     (not (clear ?y))
16     (clear ?x)
17     (handempty)
18     (on ?x ?y)))
19 ...
```

Code 2.5.2: Excerpt from a domain file

The excerpt shown above is of the "domain.pddl"² file that explains the Blocks world problem. Displayed are definitions of the "put-down" and "stack" actions, specifying the parameters required for each action, the preconditions that must

²File from: <https://github.com/mischidream/PlanPilotpp>

be met, and the corresponding effect of the action. For example, for "put-down", one block is affected. Before this action can be carried out, this block needs to be in the hand (for a block x: "holding x"). The effect is that the block is no longer held ("handempty" and "not holding x"), it has nothing stacked on top ("clear x"), and lies on the table ("ontable x").

3 PlanPilot

PlanPilot³ [6] is an interactive tool that allows the user not just to see the plans but also to explore the plan and facet spaces. In planning, most solvers show users only the best plan, but leave no room for customization or deeper reasoning why a certain plan is the best. PlanPilot, on the other hand, makes it possible for users to easily edit plans, look into specific actions, their impact on possibilities, and all possible solutions.

Figure 1: The components of PlanPilot [6]

As shown in *Figure 1* above, PlanPilot is based internally on various different components that work together. These four individual components are now explained below, as well as the way of controlling the system in interactive mode.

³PlanPilot with GUI: <https://github.com/mischidream/PlanPilotpp>,
Legacy version of PlanPilot: <https://github.com/abcorrea/planpilot>

3.1 Fast Downward

Fast Downward⁴ [7] is a classical planning system that is used to solve deterministic planning problems defined in PDDL using heuristic forward search and hierarchical problem decomposition. Plans are computed via heuristic search within the world state space reachable from the initial situation. In contrast to other planners, Fast Downward uses causal graph heuristic (calculated by hierarchical decomposition of planning tasks) as the heuristic evaluation function.

The plan solving process of Fast Downward is split into three phases:

- Translation: The input is translated from PDDL into a non-binary form. Syntactic structures are then removed with normalization and invariant synthesis methods to locate groupings of related proportions. The product of this process is a multi-valued planning task. In a multi-valued planning task, instead of having multiple boolean flags (e.g., is-at-location-A, is-at-location-B), a single multi-valued variable is able to store a set of values directly (e.g., {A, B, ...}).
- Knowledge compilation: Four different data structures are generated, which are later used in the search phase. They, namely, are:
 - Domain transition graph: Represents how each variable can change its value and which conditions need to be fulfilled
 - Causal graph: Showing the interdependencies of state variables
 - Successor generator: Used to determine the feasible operators in a given state
 - Axiom evaluator: Used to calculate the values for the derived variables
- Search: In this phase, the algorithms "greedy best-first search", "multi-heuristic best-first search", and "focused iterative-broadening" are used to find solutions.

⁴<https://www.fast-downward.org/latest/>

3.2 Plasp

Plasp⁵ [8] is a system that translates planning problems written in PDDL into ASP facts, which can then be solved by an ASP solver such as "clingo". It is developed primarily by the Potassco⁶ group at the University of Potsdam. The system provides a framework for ASP-based planning and supports different planning strategies, including sequential and parallel planning, using incremental ASP solving. The program also offers options for preprocessing the input via Fast Downward.

3.3 Clingo

Clingo⁷ [9] is an ASP system of the Potassco⁶ group of the university of Potsdam that not only solves a logic program once, but processes it within a continuously evolving workflow. It is a combination of a grounder and a solver that operates within a single process. A grounder is used to translate a task described in PDDL to a grounded representation of the task [10] where all abstract actions and variables have been instantiated with concrete, specific objects.

Not being forced to redundantly restart the solver and grounder allows clingo to handle newly added rules, modified data, and external inputs, without restarting from scratch each time and is the core idea of multi-shot ASP solving. It is especially useful for problems where rules or input data change over time because it enables the user to dynamically build and control the system during runtime.

⁵<https://github.com/potassco/plasp>

⁶<https://potassco.org/>

⁷<https://github.com/potassco/clingo>

3.4 Fasb

The Faceted Answer Set Browser⁸ (fasb) [11] is a tool built on top of the ASP solver "clingo". It enables interactive exploration of large answer set spaces. Instead of computing and manually inspecting all solutions of an ASP program, fasb allows users to navigate through the solution space using facets.

The system makes it possible to restrict the current set of answer sets step by step. A user can select facets, and fasb adds the corresponding constraints. As a result, only the answer sets that satisfy the chosen facet remain available. Through a sequence of such navigation steps, the user can either quickly narrow the search space toward a single solution or gradually explore alternative subspaces. Additionally, the option exists to backtrack or remove facet selections to explore different branches of the solution space, ensuring interactive and non-linear navigation.

To support efficient navigation, fasb uses facet weights. These weights estimate how strongly a selected facet affects the remaining solution space and help guide the navigation process.

⁸<https://github.com/drwadu/fasb>

3.5 Interactive Mode

When all the components stated above work together, as seen in *Figure 1*, the user can work with PlanPilot by using the following fasb commands⁹:

- "! n": Lists out "n" number of possible plans for the solution of the problem
- "?": Lists all facets
- "#!": Shows the number of possible plans
- "#?": Shows the number of existing facets
- "#!!": Lists all positive and negative facets, including the values for:
 - remaining.solutions.positive (amount of solutions remaining if the facet is activated)
 - remaining.solutions.negative (amount of solutions remaining if the facet is deactivated)
 - reduction.solutions.positive (reduction percentage of the remaining solutions if the facet is activated)
 - reduction.solutions.negative (reduction percentage of the remaining solutions if the facet is deactivated)
- "#??": Lists all positive and negative facets, including the values for:
 - remaining.facets.positive (amount of facets remaining for future de-activation if the facet is activated)
 - remaining.facets.negative (amount of facets remaining for future de-activation if the facet is deactivated)
 - reduction.facets.positive (reduction percentage of the remaining facets for future de-activation if the facet is activated)
 - reduction.facets.negative (reduction percentage of the remaining facets for future de-activation if the facet is deactivated)
- "| = %": Lists all landmarks (mandatory actions at a time step, these are the facets that have to occur in every possible plan)

⁹Commands from the README.md of: <https://github.com/abcorrea/planpilot>

- "+ occurs(...)": Activates a facet (sets the facet-state to "Selected")
- "- occurs(...)": Removes the activation of a facet (sets the facet-state to "Not selected" when the facet is activated)
- "+ ~occurs(...)": Deactivates a facet (sets the facet-state to "Forbidden")
- "- ~occurs(...)": Removes the deactivation of a facet (sets the facet-state to "Not selected" when the facet is deactivated)

3.5.1 Facet States

As described in the commands, there are three possible facet states: "Not selected", "Selected", and "Forbidden". The neutral state in which all facets are in the beginning is "Not selected", as they are neither activated nor deactivated. If a facets becomes a forced action through the activation command, its state changes to "Selected". On the contrary, a facet has the state "Forbidden" when its deactivated by using the fitting command.

By changing the facets states, PlanPilot allows the user to customize plans and understand the impact of actions when executed at certain time steps of a plan. This allows exploration of the plan space instead of just a simple output of what is considered the best plan.

4 PlanningCopilot

The PlanningCopilot is an attempt to realize explainable AI Planning (XAIP) [12]. XAIP aims to improve the understandability and accessibility of planning systems for users.

LLMs have been experimented with in a wide variety of ways within the context of planning. In the NL2Plan project [13] for example, an LLM was utilized to generate a problem defined in PDDL, based on natural-language explanations provided by users. The generated problem was subsequently solved by a classical planner.

However, the task of the PlanningCopilot is to receive requests in plain text from a user, turn them into commands to control PlanPilot, and then explain the output given by the system.

4.1 Implementation

For the implementation of the PlanningCopilot, the model "ChatGPT-5.4" of OpenAI was used. The model was not specifically trained for this purpose and was selected due to its exceptionally large input token size.

The program is based on the web interface version of PlanPilot³, but the interface was not utilized for the project to avoid problems that arise from its complicated structure. The entire system is written in Python code. In the code, the LLM is given a predefined tool, called "send_planpilot_command", to execute commands in PlanPilot. All other functionality is specified in the definitions within the system prompt. There, the LLM is given the context of how to react in certain situations, e.g., when to use which command, how to respond to user questions regarding the output of PlanPilot, and also the general context in which it is situated is explained. Some general rules for the responses are also stated, for example, how to display the information and how detailed the explanation should be.

When started, the PlanningCopilot automatically runs Fast Downward with the domain and problem files written in PDDL that are stated in the code. After that, the LLM is initialized with the system prompt, then the user can write commands, ask questions, and type orders into the terminal. The LLM converts this input into the necessary commands to receive the wanted information or to

implement requested changes. Thereafter, the commands are executed in the PlanPilot application and the received information is explained.

All fasb commands are defined to the LLM within the system prompt in such a way that it is able to use them. In these explanations, examples are given, for instance, when the commands should be used, as well as the expected output from PlanPilot and how to interpret the said output. Furthermore, the concept of a FACET_ID is specified to the LLM, this is the exact title of a facet returned by the commands listing all facets ("?", "#??" and "#!!"). The usage of FACET_IDs is necessary to ensure the correct modification of facet states.

4.2 Summary of the System Prompt Content

The following rules are specified within the system prompt to ensure correct answers. They are listed in the order of their appearance in the code.

PLANPILOT COMMAND RULES: All possible commands for PlanPilot are listed and explained. Additionally, the concept of a FACET_ID is introduced to the LLM.

FACET STATE SEMANTICS AND EFFECT: Explains the activation/deactivation commands and their counterparts, as well as the exact order of commands needed, when the user wants to directly change from activation to deactivation or vice versa. This is explicitly stated in order not to forget the neutral state during the modification process.

ACTION INTENT DETECTION: Helps the LLM to understand the intent of the user in the case of wanting a facet to be activated, deactivated, or set to neutral.

FACET METRICS INTERPRETATION: Explains the meaning of the metrics returned by the commands "#??" and "#!!" (reduction.facets.* and remaining.facets.*, reduction.solution.* and remaining.solution.*)¹⁰. In addition, the LLM is instructed on how to display and explain the information of the metrics to the user.

PLAN QUERIES: Explains the command "! n" due to the requirement that the LLM has to replace n with the desired number of plans to be returned.

PLAN TABLE CREATION: Shows how to convert a plan into a table for better display. This also allows for easier facet comparison, for example, to find alternatives.

ALTERNATIVE FACETS ANALYSIS: Explains how to act when the user wants to know alternative facets to the ones currently represented in the plan. In this rule, it is defined which facets count as alternatives and in which way the information has to be conveyed to the user.

¹⁰"*" represents the positive and negative parameters.

FACET MATCHING RULE: This rule establishes to match facets by FACET_ID due to the commands "?", "#??" and "#!!" returning different data, and the LLM must understand that this information belongs to the same facet and not to different ones.

FACET CONSTRUCTION RULE: For the activation, deactivation, and return to neutrality of facets, it is necessary to correctly insert the FACET_ID into the commands. The rule also forbids the LLM from guessing or constructing the IDs on its own, but it is allowed and instructed to reuse FACET_IDs used before.

SELECTION STATES: Explanation of the three facet states ("Selected", "Forbidden", and "Not selected") due to the mismatch of them being referred to as activated, deactivated, and neutral in natural language.

EXAMPLE REASONING: Provides, through an explicit walkthrough, a detailed example of exactly how alternatives should be identified and presented.

ALTERNATIVE OUTPUT FORMAT: Tells the LLM to group alternatives by timestep for a clearer display of the information.

FACET SELECTION: Explains which commands to use for the activation, deactivation, and the removal of an activation or deactivation. The rule also forces the LLM to check the current state of a facet before changing the state. This is done to ensure that the undesired state is neutral, so that a facet cannot be activated and deactivated at the same time.

FACET MEMORY RULE: Sometimes it is mandatory to remember the FACET_ID of a facet because the facets are removed from the facet lists when activated or deactivated. Therefore, the framework of this is set up, so that the LLM understands when it is important to memorize a FACET_ID and when it is allowed to use it.

FINAL VERIFICATION RULE: To prevent wrongfully reported facet alternatives, this rule forces the LLM to once again check if the alternatives found are correct.

SWAP DETECTION: Defines what a swap is and explains how to detect them in case a user requests to scan for swaps.

PLANNING ANALYSIS QUESTIONS: The most common questions in planning and the possible ways to answer them are described in detail. Several examples are provided of how a user could formulate these questions. Through this, correct and detailed answers are ensured. These questions are as follows.

- QUESTION: CURRENT PLAN
- QUESTION: NUMBER OF SOLUTIONS
- QUESTION: ALTERNATIVE ACTIONS
- QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
- QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE
- QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR SOLUTIONS
- QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR FACETS
- QUESTION: FORCED ACTIONS
- QUESTION: PLAN CHANGE EFFECT
- QUESTION: SWAP DETECTION
- QUESTION: APPLY CONSTRAINT
- QUESTION: ADD PREFERRED ACTION

REFERENCE RULE: Due to prior issues where the LLM thought that all facets in possible plans are activated, this rule shows the LLM the correct interpretation of plans and facet states.

DOMAIN UNDERSTANDING: Explains the actual meaning of values and thus allows for domain specific explanation, in this case the Beluga problem and blocks world are defined to the LLM.

STATE CONSISTENCY RULE: To ensure correct usage of facet states, the correct way to change between them is once again stated here.

ERROR PREVENTION RULE: Prevents the LLM from saying it is no longer able to modify activated/deactivated facets because of their removal from facet lists.

METRICS UPDATING RULE: Specifies that the metrics returned by the "#??" and "#!!" commands become outdated following a modification of a facet's state and must therefore be re-requested from PlanPilot.

GENERAL RULES: Important basic information for answer structure and the most important rules for handling PlanPilot.

5 Program Walkthroughs

To demonstrate how the LLM functions, two complete walkthroughs of problems follow below.

5.1 First Demonstration Walkthrough

```
1 Starting FastDownward...
2 Starting PlanPilot...
3 System ready.
4
5 Started Planning Copilot (type 'exit' to quit)
6
7 You > Can you please show me the current plan.
8 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
9
10 PlanningCopilot > Here is the current plan:
11
12 1 -> unstack(d,a)
13 2 -> put-down(d)
14 3 -> unstack(a,c)
15 4 -> put-down(a)
16 5 -> unstack(f,e)
17 6 -> stack(f,d)
18 7 -> unstack(e,b)
19 8 -> stack(e,f)
20 9 -> pick-up(b)
21 10 -> stack(b,c)
22 11 -> pick-up(a)
23 12 -> stack(a,e)
24 13 -> unstack(b,c)
25 14 -> stack(b,a)
26 15 -> pick-up(c)
27 16 -> stack(c,b)
```

Request 5.1.1: Show the current plan.

After the user asks something, the PlanningCopilot analyzes the question and should, based on the system prompt, with the PLANNING ANALYSIS QUESTIONS under QUESTION: CURRENT PLAN detect that a call of the "! 1" command is needed. As seen in the Request 5.1.1, the LLM correctly identified what to do and printed out the plan.

```

1 You > What is the most restrictive facet in the problem?
2 Executing PlanPilot command: #!!
3 Executing PlanPilot command: #??
4
5 PlanningCopilot > The most restrictive facet overall is:
6
7 occurs(action(("stack","b","e")),8)
8
9 Why:
10 - For plan space:
11   - Activating it removes 99.80 percent of plans
12   - Only 1 plan remains
13 - For facet space:
14   - Activating it removes 100 percent of remaining facets
15   - 0 further facets remain activatable or deactivatable
16
17 So this is the strongest restriction I found overall, and the restrictive side is activation.
18
19 Two other equally extreme facet-space cases are:
20 - occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),5)
21 - occurs(action(("unstack","b","e")),9)
22
23 They also reduce the facet space to 0 remaining facets when activated.
24
25 If you want, I can also show:
26 - the top 3 most restrictive facets for plan space only, or
27 - the top 3 most restrictive facets for facet space only.

```

Request 5.1.2: What is the most restrictive facet in the problem?

For the second question, the LLM needs to combine two pre-described questions, the QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE and QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE. In each, the handling of the respective metrics is explained. Only one of the two definitions is addressed in the System Prompt Excerpt 5.1.1, but both are similar to each other and differ solely in the metrics examined.

```

1 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
2 Intent:
3 The user wants to know which decisions restrict the solution space most
4
5 Example user requests:
6 - Which decisions reduce the solution space?
7 - Which actions remove many plans?
8 - Which decisions are restrictive for solutions?
9 - Which choices eliminate many alternative plans?
10 - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to activation?
11 - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to deactivation?
12
13 Required action:
14 Step 1:
15 Call:
16 #!!
17 Step 2:
18 If the user wants to know the restriction of the activation of the facet do the following
19 - For each facet consider:
20 - reduction.solution.positive (activation)
21 - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
22 - Highlight the most restrictive ones
23
24 If the user wants to know the restriction of the deactivation of the facet do the following
25 - For each facet consider:
26 - reduction.solution.negative (deactivation)
27 - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
28 - Highlight the most restrictive ones
29
30 If the user does not specify whether the restriction for activation or deactivation is wanted do the following
31 - For each facet consider both:
32 - reduction.solution.positive (activation)
33 - reduction.solution.negative (deactivation)
34 - Rank facets by the strongest reduction (max of both)
35 - For each facet:Identify whether activation or deactivation is more restrictive
36 - Highlight the most restrictive ones
37 Step 3:
38 For the three most restrictive facets:
39 - Explain:
40 - How many plans are removed
41 - Explain the trade-off:
42 "This decision strongly reduces the number of plans."
43
44 If the user asks for reduction of plan and facet space together, combine the results of:
45 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE
46 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
47 (Also do this when asked for the most restrictive facet and it is not specified that its only for facetspace or
planspace)

```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.1.1: QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE

As shown above for the solution space, due to the fact that the LLM learns via pattern recognition, a small variety of questions asking the same response is given. This is followed by detailed instructions on how to give the required answer and explanation.

Step 1 shows exactly which command is necessary to receive the needed information from PlanPilot.

In Step 2 it is stated which part of the information is relevant to the user's question. This is done through if-clauses filtering if the user wants to know the restriction on the amount of possible solutions in case of facet activation, deactivation or both.

In the final step (Step 3), it is determined what is displayed to the user and how the data has to be explained. Following is the ruling for the current case, when the statistics for both facet space and solution space are asked for at the

same time. The LLM is told to combine the results of the two definitions for space reduction. For this process, no further instructions need to be given to the LLM as it is capable to stitch the answer together with the provided instructions.

```
1 You > Show me the 3 most restrictive facets for the facet space.
2 Executing PlanPilot command: #??
3
4 PlanningCopilot > Here are the 3 most restrictive facets for facet space:
5
6 1. occurs(action(("stack","b","e")),8)
7 - Most restrictive side: activation
8 - Activating it removes 100 percent of future facets
9 - 0 facets remain activatable or deactivatable
10
11 2. occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),5)
12 - Most restrictive side: activation
13 - Activating it removes 100 percent of future facets
14 - 0 facets remain activatable or deactivatable
15
16 3. occurs(action(("unstack","b","e")),9)
17 - Most restrictive side: activation
18 - Activating it removes 100 percent of future facets
19 - 0 facets remain activatable or deactivatable
20
21 Trade-off:
22 These decisions are maximally restrictive for the facet space. If you activate one of them, there are no further facet
    choices left.
```

Request 5.1.3: The three most restrictive facets for the facet space.

At the end of the answer, the LLM directly offers the user a possible way to continue the planning space exploration. This is an advantage of working with an LLM, as it tries to help the user get the wanted information by suggesting possible next steps. In this case, the user takes the suggestion and asks one of the questions mentioned by the PlanningCopilot. The question is then answered by following the same procedure as mentioned in System Prompt Excerpt 5.1.1.

```
1 You > Is there a facet that leaves only two plans left?
2 Executing PlanPilot command: #!!
3
4 PlanningCopilot > Yes.
5
6 There are several facets that leave exactly 2 plans when activated. Examples include:
7
8 - occurs(action(("unstack","f","d")),3)
9 - occurs(action(("unstack","c","b")),13)
10 - occurs(action(("stack","a","d")),4)
11 - occurs(action(("stack","c","b")),12)
12 - occurs(action(("unstack","a","e")),7)
13 - occurs(action(("put-down","c")),8)
14 - occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),7)
15 - occurs(action(("pick-up","f")),3)
16 - occurs(action(("unstack","e","b")),3)
17 - occurs(action(("unstack","a","f")),7)
18
19 Effect:
20 - Activating any of these removes 99.61 percent of plans
21 - 2 plans remain
22
23 If you want, I can also list all such facets.
```

Request 5.1.4: Is there a facet that leaves only two plans left?

To answer this user question, the LLM needs to use its knowledge of the FACET METRIC INTERPRETATION rule. There, the meaning of the metrics from

the PlanPilot commands "#??" and "#!!" is explained in detail.

```
1 FACET METRICS INTERPRETATION
2 [...]
3 Plan Space Metrics (#!!):
4 Facets returned by the #!! command contain additional metrics describing how the facet affects the solution space
5
6 Each facet contains the following fields:
7 reduction.solution.positive
8 reduction.solution.negative
9 remaining.solution.positive
10 remaining.solution.negative
11
12 The values of reduction.solution.positive and reduction.solution.negative are fractions where:
13 1.0 = 100 percent of solutions
14 0.5 = 50 percent of solutions
15 0.34 = 34 percent of solutions
16
17 Interpretation rules:
18 reduction.solution.positive
19 Percentage of solutions removed if the facet is activated
20
21 reduction.solution.negative
22 Percentage of solutions removed if the facet is deactivated
23
24 remaining.solution.positive
25 Amount of solutions that remain if the facet is activated
26
27 remaining.solution.negative
28 Amount of solutions that remain if the facet is deactivated
29
30 Example:
31 Facet:
32 pick-up(e) at timestep 3
33
34 reduction.solution.positive = 0.9415
35 reduction.solution.negative = 0.0585
36 remaining.solution.positive = 49.0
37 remaining.solution.negative = 789.0
38
39 Interpretation:
40 If this facet is activated:
41 94.15 percent of the possible plans will be removed
42 49 possible plans remain afterwards
43 If this facet is deactivated:
44 5.85 percent of the possible plans will be removed
45 789 possible plans remain afterwards
46
47 Example explanation:
48 "Activating this facet removes 94.15 percent possible plans and leaves 49 possible solutions.
49 Deactivating this facet removes 5.85 percent of available plans and 789 plans will remain."
50 [...]
```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.1.2: FACET METRICS INTERPRETATION

Above, the relevant part for the solution space metrics is shown. The meaning of the values returned from "#!!" for reduction.solution.positive/.negative and remaining.solution.positive/.negative are explained. The LLM knows nothing about them beforehand, which makes it necessary to mention everything important so that it is possible to understand what it is dealing with. This means that the data types of the metrics, the overall meaning, as well as how these must be presented to the user need to be explained. As seen above, all of this is first defined for the LLM, then an example on how to possibly convey the information follows.

```

1 You > And when deactivated?
2 Executing PlanPilot command: #!!
3
4 PlanningCopilot > No.
5
6 In the current data, there is no facet that leaves exactly 2 plans when deactivated.
7
8 The smallest numbers of remaining plans I can see for deactivation are larger, for example:
9 - occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),15) -> deactivated leaves 28 plans
10 - occurs(action(("stack","b","a")),14) -> deactivated leaves 56 plans
11 - occurs(action(("unstack","d","a")),1) -> deactivated leaves 64 plans
12
13 So exactly 2 remaining plans appears only for activation, not for deactivation.

```

Request 5.1.5: Is there a facet that leaves only two plans left when deactivated?

For this question, no new rules are needed. The ones stated by the FACET METRICS INTERPRETATION are used once again.

```

1 You > Then please activate stack(a,d) in step 4 and explain the difference of the two remaining plans to me.
2 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
3 Executing PlanPilot command: ?
4 Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("stack","a","d")),4)
5 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
6 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 2
7
8 PlanningCopilot > I activated the facet:
9
10 - occurs(action(("stack","a","d")),4)
11
12 New current plan:
13 1 -> unstack(d,a)
14 2 -> put-down(d)
15 3 -> unstack(a,c)
16 4 -> stack(a,d)
17 5 -> unstack(a,d)
18 6 -> stack(a,c)
19 7 -> unstack(f,e)
20 8 -> stack(f,d)
21 9 -> unstack(e,b)
22 10 -> stack(e,f)
23 11 -> unstack(a,c)
24 12 -> stack(a,e)
25 13 -> pick-up(b)
26 14 -> stack(b,a)
27 15 -> pick-up(c)
28 16 -> stack(c,b)
29
30 Difference to the previous reference plan:
31 - Step 4 changed from put-down(a) to stack(a,d)
32 - Step 5 changed from unstack(f,e) to unstack(a,d)
33 - Step 6 changed from stack(f,d) to stack(a,c)
34 - The handling of f and e is shifted later:
35   - old: 5 unstack(f,e), 6 stack(f,d), 7 unstack(e,b), 8 stack(e,f)
36   - new: 7 unstack(f,e), 8 stack(f,d), 9 unstack(e,b), 10 stack(e,f)
37
38 Difference between the two remaining plans:
39
40 Plan 1:
41 - 5 -> unstack(a,d)
42 - 6 -> stack(a,c)
43 - 11 -> unstack(a,c)
44
45 Plan 2:
46 - 5 -> unstack(a,d)
47 - 6 -> put-down(a)
48 - 11 -> pick-up(a)
49
50 So the key difference is how a is handled after unstacking it from d:
51 - In plan 1, a is immediately stacked onto c at step 6, and later removed from c at step 11
52 - In plan 2, a is put down at step 6, and later picked up again at step 11
53
54 Everything else is the same in both remaining plans.

```

Request 5.1.6: Activate stack(a,d) in step 4 and explain the difference of the two remaining plans.

To fulfill this user request, the LLM must know exactly how to activate and/or deactivate a facet. For that, the possible facet states are defined in SELECTION STATES. These states are: Forbidden (deactivated), Selected (activated) and Not selected (neutral). Just stating the definition of the facet states is not enough to make modifications possible for the LLM. FACET STATE SEMANTICS AND EFFECT shows the right way to alter states and also directly defines specific procedures in order to prevent certain errors.

```

1  FACET STATE SEMANTICS AND EFFECT
2  Semantics:
3    + occurs(A, T)
4      forces the action A to occur at timestep T (facet is activated)
5      executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
6        + FACET_ID
7
8    - occurs(A, T)
9      removes the activation (set to neutral)
10     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
11       - FACET_ID
12
13    + ~occurs(A, T)
14     forbids the action A at timestep T (facet is deactivated)
15     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
16       + ~FACET_ID
17
18    - ~occurs(A, T)
19     removes the deactivation (set to neutral)
20     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
21       - ~FACET_ID
22
23  Important:
24    - "+ occurs(A,T)" enforces an action
25    - "+ ~occurs(A,T)" forbids an action
26    - "- occurs(A,T)" resets an activation to neutral
27    - "- ~occurs(A,T)" resets an deactivation to neutral
28    - Use exact FACET_ID from ?, #?? or #!! (only call one)
29    - "" must be included exactly as described
30
31  Execution rule:
32    If activation is requested:
33      You must first check the current selectionState:
34        - If Selected:
35          Do nothing (already selected)
36        - If Forbidden:
37          run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
38          run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
39        - If Not selected:
40          run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
41
42    If deactivation is requested:
43      You must first check the current selectionState:
44        - If Selected:
45          run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
46          run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
47        - If Forbidden:
48          Do nothing (already forbidden)
49        - If Not selected:
50          run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
51
52    To remove activation or deactivation:
53      You must first check the current selectionState:
54        - If Selected:
55          run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
56        - If Forbidden:
57          run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
58        - If Not selected: Do nothing (already not selected)
59
60  Never confuse removing a modification (- FACET_ID or - ~FACET_ID) with forbidding an action (+ ~FACET_ID)

```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.1.3: FACET STATE SEMANTICS AND EFFECT

The rule starts by stating which PlanPilot commands correspond to each of the facet states. Then some additional rules follow to help prevent errors, for example, a reminder to not omit "~" when executing. Furthermore, to hinder issues, an execution rule states which commands are necessary for each possible user request and also the possible state a facet is in before modification. In addition to this, it is precisely explained how to call "run_planpilot_command" with these commands to ensure that the copilot only sends the correct commands to PlanPilot.

```
1 You > But step 5 is the same.
2
3 PlanningCopilot > You are right.
4
5 Step 5 is the same in both remaining plans:
6 - 5 -> unstack(a,d)
7
8 The actual difference between the two remaining plans is:
9
10 Plan 1
11 - 6 -> stack(a,c)
12 - 11 -> unstack(a,c)
13
14 Plan 2
15 - 6 -> put-down(a)
16 - 11 -> pick-up(a)
17
18 So the difference is only in how a is stored between steps 6 and 11:
19 - Plan 1 keeps a on c
20 - Plan 2 keeps a on the table
21
22 All other steps are identical.
```

Request 5.1.7: Point out that step 5 is the same.

Already visible in the previous question is the error that the LLM is being alerted to here. The facet `unstack(a,d)` in time step 5 is listed as a difference in the two plans, even though this is not correct since it appears in both plans. What this shows is a rare problem that can occasionally occur. PlanPilot delivers the correct information, the LLM has the right way of working with the information defined in the system prompt, but still comes to the wrong conclusion. However, this may be an error by the LLM, but it is not a hallucination, as the data is actually present and not fabricated. The main problem stems from the fact that the LLM will always present its answers as correct regardless of whether they actually are or not.

```

1  You > Reset the activation and please tell me if there are any landmarks in the problem.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("stack","a","d")),4)
3  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
4  Executing PlanPilot command: |= %
5
6  PlanningCopilot > I reset the activation.
7
8  Current plan:
9  1 -> unstack(d,a)
10 2 -> put-down(d)
11 3 -> unstack(f,e)
12 4 -> stack(f,d)
13 5 -> unstack(e,b)
14 6 -> stack(e,a)
15 7 -> unstack(e,a)
16 8 -> put-down(e)
17 9 -> pick-up(e)
18 10 -> stack(e,f)
19 11 -> unstack(a,c)
20 12 -> stack(a,e)
21 13 -> pick-up(b)
22 14 -> stack(b,a)
23 15 -> pick-up(c)
24 16 -> stack(c,b)
25
26 Yes, there is a landmark in the problem:
27
28 - Step 16: stack(c,b)
29   - FACET_ID: occurs(action(("stack","c","b")),16)
30
31 This means that this action is forced:
32 - no alternative facet exists for this step
33 - every valid plan must contain this action at step 16

```

Request 5.1.8: Are there any landmarks in the problem?

Resetting any modifications, as in this user request, is made possible through the FACET MEMORY RULE. After each modification, the LLM is tasked with remembering the FACET_IDS of the said facets, to then reuse them in case the modifications need to be reversed or new modifications with these facets are wanted. This is necessary because activated/deactivated facets are not listed in the commands returning the facet space, so in order to remain capable of enacting user orders, the facets need to be memorized.

The question shown in Request 5.1.8 also clearly demonstrates how easily the LLM can execute multiple commands in order to obtain all the information needed for the answer. This is evident in the removal of the facet activation and the display of the landmarks.

```
1 You > How many plans and facets exist?
2 Executing PlanPilot command: #!
3 Executing PlanPilot command: #?
4
5 PlanningCopilot > There are:
6 - 508 plans
7 - 276 facets
```

Request 5.1.9: How many plans and facets exist?

As mentioned, when multiple commands are required to be executed, the system ensures simple and efficient output. Here, for both the number of facets and possible plans.

```
1 You > What alternatives are there in time step 11 to the facet in the current plan?
2 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
3 Executing PlanPilot command: ?
4
5 PlanningCopilot > Current plan at step 11:
6 - 11 -> unstack(a,c)
7
8 Alternatives at step 11 are:
9 - pick-up(a)
10 - unstack(c,a)
11 - unstack(b,a)
12 - pick-up(c)
13 - unstack(a,e)
14 - unstack(b,c)
15
16 These are the valid alternative facets for timestep 11 because they are at the same timestep and differ from the current action.
```

Request 5.1.10: What alternatives are there in time step 11 to the facet in the current plan?

Having the ability to correctly identify possible alternatives in the desired step is derived from the ALTERNATIVE FACETS ANALYSIS. Facets are only considered alternatives if their time steps match the named time step and if both the actions and objects involved differ from those in the plan's facet. When given the order to check for alternatives, the LLM first shows itself all facets via the PlanPilot command "?" and then filters them by the aforementioned criteria.

```

1 You > Can you activate pick up c in this step and show me a plan with as little change to the current as possible.
2 Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),11)
3 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
4
5 PlanningCopilot > I activated:
6 - occurs(action(("pick-up","c")),11)
7
8 Plan with that choice:
9 1 -> unstack(f,e)
10 2 -> put-down(f)
11 3 -> unstack(d,a)
12 4 -> put-down(d)
13 5 -> pick-up(f)
14 6 -> stack(f,d)
15 7 -> unstack(e,b)
16 8 -> stack(e,f)
17 9 -> unstack(a,c)
18 10 -> stack(a,e)
19 11 -> pick-up(c)
20 12 -> put-down(c)
21 13 -> pick-up(b)
22 14 -> stack(b,a)
23 15 -> pick-up(c)
24 16 -> stack(c,b)
25
26 Main differences to the previous current plan:
27 - Step 11 changed from unstack(a,c) to pick-up(c)
28 - Step 12 changed from stack(a,e) to put-down(c)
29
30 There are also earlier changes:
31 - Steps 1-10 were reorganized, so this is not just a local change around step 11
32
33 So PlanPilot found a valid plan with pick-up(c) at step 11, but it does not stay very close to the previous plan overall.
34 If you want, I can now look for:
35 - alternatives at nearby steps to reduce the disturbance, or
- the impact of this activated facet on the remaining plan space.

```

Request 5.1.11: Activate pick-up c in this step and show a plan with as little change to the current as possible.

The user now requests to activate a facet and be shown a plan with as little change to the plan that was displayed the response before as possible. Through this, another small issue is visible, here the LLM only takes the first step towards fulfilling the users request. Then it pauses and asks for confirmation if it should actually enact the desired action.

```

1  You > Check for other plans closer to the one you showed me before.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 5
3
4  PlanningCopilot > I checked more plans with pick-up(c) at step 11.
5
6  The closest one to the plan before the change is solution 3:
7
8  1 -> unstack(d,a)
9  2 -> put-down(d)
10 3 -> unstack(f,e)
11 4 -> stack(f,d)
12 5 -> unstack(a,c)
13 6 -> stack(a,c)
14 7 -> unstack(e,b)
15 8 -> stack(e,f)
16 9 -> unstack(a,c)
17 10 -> stack(a,e)
18 11 -> pick-up(c)
19 12 -> put-down(c)
20 13 -> pick-up(b)
21 14 -> stack(b,a)
22 15 -> pick-up(c)
23 16 -> stack(c,b)
24
25 Compared to the earlier plan I showed before activation:
26 1 -> unstack(d,a)
27 2 -> put-down(d)
28 3 -> unstack(f,e)
29 4 -> stack(f,d)
30 5 -> unstack(e,b)
31 6 -> stack(e,a)
32 7 -> unstack(e,a)
33 8 -> put-down(e)
34 9 -> pick-up(e)
35 10 -> stack(e,f)
36 11 -> unstack(a,c)
37 12 -> stack(a,e)
38 13 -> pick-up(b)
39 14 -> stack(b,a)
40 15 -> pick-up(c)
41 16 -> stack(c,b)
42
43 The unchanged steps are:
44 - 1, 2, 3, 4
45 - 13, 14, 15, 16
46
47 The main changes are:
48 - step 11 is now pick-up(c), as requested
49 - step 12 becomes put-down(c)
50 - steps 5-10 are reorganized
51
52 So yes, there are plans closer to the original one than the first plan I showed, and solution 3 is currently the closest
    among the first five I checked.

```

Request 5.1.12: Check for plans closer to the one shown before.

After the user approves the action, the copilot without problem checks the first five plans comparing them to the primary plan and then highlights the user the differences. For this, no specific definition is needed within the system prompt.

```

1  You > How many plans are there?
2  Executing PlanPilot command: #!
3
4  PlanningCopilot > There are 29 plans.
5
6  You > Check all 29.
7  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 29
8
9  PlanningCopilot > I checked all 29 plans.
10
11 The closest plans to the previous plan are solutions 16 and 17. They preserve the most structure of the earlier plan while
    keeping:
12
13 - 11 -> pick-up(c)
14
15 Best match found: solution 16
16 1 -> unstack(d,a)
17 2 -> put-down(d)
18 3 -> unstack(f,e)
19 4 -> stack(f,d)
20 5 -> unstack(e,b)
21 6 -> stack(e,a)
22 7 -> unstack(e,a)
23 8 -> stack(e,f)
24 9 -> unstack(a,c)
25 10 -> stack(a,e)
26 11 -> pick-up(c)
27 12 -> put-down(c)
28 13 -> pick-up(b)
29 14 -> stack(b,a)
30 15 -> pick-up(c)
31 16 -> stack(c,b)
32
33 Compared to the earlier plan before activation:
34 1 -> unstack(d,a)
35 2 -> put-down(d)
36 3 -> unstack(f,e)
37 4 -> stack(f,d)
38 5 -> unstack(e,b)
39 6 -> stack(e,a)
40 7 -> unstack(e,a)
41 8 -> put-down(e)
42 9 -> pick-up(e)
43 10 -> stack(e,f)
44 11 -> unstack(a,c)
45 12 -> stack(a,e)
46 13 -> pick-up(b)
47 14 -> stack(b,a)
48 15 -> pick-up(c)
49 16 -> stack(c,b)
50
51 Differences:
52 - step 8: put-down(e) -> stack(e,f)
53 - step 9: pick-up(e) -> unstack(a,c)
54 - step 10: stack(e,f) -> stack(a,e)
55 - step 11: unstack(a,c) -> pick-up(c)
56 - step 12: stack(a,e) -> put-down(c)
57
58 Unchanged:
59 - steps 1-7
60 - steps 13-16
61
62 So this is a much closer plan than the first one I showed after activation. The requested choice at step 11 forces some
    downstream changes, but this plan keeps the prefix and suffix mostly intact.

```

Request 5.1.13: How many plans are there? Then check all for the closest to the previous plan.

To test the capability of the system to work with larger amounts of data, the user tasks the LLM to compare all the remaining 29 plans to the primary plan. What would take a human by hand multiple minutes is done by the LLM within seconds. This concludes the first demonstration walkthrough.

5.2 Second Demonstration Walkthrough

```
1 Starting FastDownward...
2 Starting PlanPilot...
3 System ready.
4
5 Started the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot (type 'exit' to quit).
6
7 While activating or deactivating facets always state the time step to prevent errors.
8
9 You > Please show me the current plan.
10 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
11
12 PlanningCopilot > Current plan:
13
14 1 -> unstack(c,e)
15 2 -> put-down(c)
16 3 -> unstack(e,b)
17 4 -> put-down(e)
18 5 -> pick-up(d)
19 6 -> stack(d,c)
20 7 -> pick-up(e)
21 8 -> put-down(e)
22 9 -> unstack(b,a)
23 10 -> stack(b,d)
24 11 -> pick-up(e)
25 12 -> stack(e,b)
26 13 -> pick-up(a)
27 14 -> stack(a,e)
```

Request 5.2.1: Please show the current plan.

Identical to the first walkthrough, the first plan is made visible. Unlike in the PlanPilot application, the plan is printed in a formatted form. When receiving the plan through the "! 1" command, the LLM is forced through the PLAN TABLE CREATION rule to, create a table where the plan is structured. This is done not only to give the LLM a better overview of the data but also to present it more clearly to the user.

```

1  You > Are there any swaps in this plan?
2  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
3
4  PlanningCopilot > Yes, there appears to be a likely swap involving block e.
5
6  Plan table:
7  1 -> unstack(c,e)
8  2 -> put-down(c)
9  3 -> unstack(e,b)
10 4 -> put-down(e)
11 5 -> pick-up(d)
12 6 -> stack(d,c)
13 7 -> pick-up(e)
14 8 -> put-down(e)
15 9 -> unstack(b,a)
16 10 -> stack(b,d)
17 11 -> pick-up(e)
18 12 -> stack(e,b)
19 13 -> pick-up(a)
20 14 -> stack(a,e)
21
22 Likely swap:
23 - 3 -> unstack(e,b)
24 - 4 -> put-down(e)
25 - 7 -> pick-up(e)
26 - 8 -> put-down(e)
27 - 11 -> pick-up(e)
28 - 12 -> stack(e,b)
29
30 Why this looks like a swap:
31 - e is moved off b at steps 3-4, which clears access to b.
32 - Then b is manipulated later at steps 9-10.
33 - e is also moved again at 7-8 without obvious progress, because it is picked up and put down again.
34 - Finally, e is moved once more at 11-12 and placed back onto b.
35
36 Strong indicator:
37 - e is moved away from a supporting position.
38 - Another object, b, is later accessed.
39 - e is then moved again and returned to a structurally relevant place.
40
41 Most suspicious unnecessary part:
42 - Step 7 -> pick-up(e)
43 - Step 8 -> put-down(e)
44
45 Those two steps especially look like a temporary relocation with no visible direct benefit in the shown action sequence.
46
47 Suggestion:
48 - Try to avoid moving e twice after it is first put down.
49 - If possible, keep e in a place where b can still be accessed, or postpone handling e until it can be placed directly in
    its useful final position.

```

Request 5.2.2: Are there any swaps in this plan?

When a user wants to check for swaps in PlanPilot, it has to be done manually by scanning the plan by hand. Now, thanks to the SWAP DETECTION definition, it is possible for the PlanningCopilot to detect swaps for the user.

```

1 SWAP DETECTION
2 A swap is a temporary action that does not contribute to the goal but only enables another action
3
4 Detection procedure:
5 Step 1:
6 Call:
7 ! 1
8 Step 2:
9 Use DOMAIN UNDERSTANDING to infer object roles:
10 - Movable objects
11 - Storage locations
12 Step 3:
13 Track object movements
14 Step 4:
15 A swap exists if:
16 - Object A is moved at t1
17 - Another object B is manipulated at t2
18 - Object A is moved again at t3
19 - And:
20 - A returns to previous or irrelevant position
21 or
22 - A was only moved to access B
23 Step 5:
24 Strong swap indicator:
25 - A is moved away from a storage location
26 - Then another object is accessed
27 - Then A is moved again
28
29 Output:
30 - List swap steps
31 - Explain why unnecessary
32 - Suggest avoiding movement or better placement

```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.2.1: SWAP DETECTION

In the above definition, the basic concept of swaps is explained. The LLM is initially instructed to gather the necessary information from PlanPilot. Then, the search for the swap begins, for which the DOMAIN UNDERSTANDING section of the system prompt is used. The section provides an explanation intended to provide the LLM with a deeper understanding of the meanings of the objects and locations within the problem. Next, the movement sequences of the objects are tracked in order to apply the given definition.

This definition states that if, at a time step t_1 , object a is moved only to then interact with an object b at a time step t_2 and then a is moved again at a time step t_3 to an unimportant position or the same position as in t_1 , so these steps are only made to gain access to b , then a swap most likely occurred. A strong indicator of a swap is when the object a is moved away from a storage location, another object is accessed, and then the object a is moved again. If a swap is detected using this method, the user is then informed of the steps involved, why these processes are unnecessary, and what actions might prevent this swap. With this definition, the LLM is able to correctly identify the suspicious movement of the block e that occurs at time steps 7 to 8 and informs the user about this swap in Request 5.2.2.

```

1  You > Please check for alternatives that could remove the swap.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
3  Executing PlanPilot command: ?
4
5  PlanningCopilot > Yes. I found several alternative actions at the suspicious swap region that could help avoid the extra
   movement of e.
6
7  Current plan table:
8  1 -> unstack(c,e)
9  2 -> put-down(c)
10 3 -> unstack(e,b)
11 4 -> put-down(e)
12 5 -> pick-up(d)
13 6 -> stack(d,c)
14 7 -> pick-up(e)
15 8 -> put-down(e)
16 9 -> unstack(b,a)
17 10 -> stack(b,d)
18 11 -> pick-up(e)
19 12 -> stack(e,b)
20 13 -> pick-up(a)
21 14 -> stack(a,e)
22
23 Most relevant swap region:
24 - Step 7: pick-up(e)
25 - Step 8: put-down(e)
26 - Step 11: pick-up(e)
27 - Step 12: stack(e,b)
28
29 Valid alternatives near that region:
30 Step 7
31 - unstack(d,b)
32 - unstack(e,d)
33 - unstack(b,a)
34 - unstack(e,b)
35 - unstack(d,e)
36 - pick-up(d)
37 - unstack(d,c)
38 Step 8
39 - stack(b,a)
40 - put-down(b)
41 - stack(b,d)
42 - stack(d,c)
43 - stack(b,e)
44 Step 11
45 - unstack(e,a)
46 - pick-up(a)
47 - unstack(e,b)
48 Step 12
49 - stack(a,e)
50 - put-down(a)
51
52 Most promising alternatives for removing the swap:
53 - Step 7: unstack(b,a)
54   This is promising because it starts working on b earlier, instead of moving e again.
55 - Step 8: stack(b,d)
56   This also looks promising because it continues the b-related goal progress directly.
57 - Step 11: pick-up(a)
58   This may avoid needing to handle e again at that point.
59 - Step 12: stack(a,e)
60   This directly supports the final action at step 14 and may reduce intermediate e movement.
61
62 Interpretation:
63 - The current swap seems to come from handling e again at steps 7-8 before b is actually manipulated at 9-10.
64 - Alternatives at steps 7-8 suggest the planner may be able to continue directly with b or d instead of performing the
   extra pick-up/put-down of e.
65 - Alternatives at steps 11-12 suggest that later progress might also be reorganized so e is not moved in such a detour.
66
67 If you want, I can next focus on: only the alternatives at steps 7 and 8, or try one specific alternative.

```

Request 5.2.3: Check for alternatives that could remove the swap.

Through the successful swap detection in the last response to the user, the copilot now uses the identified steps and checks if there are alternatives that possibly could remove the swap. In addition, the system analyzes the different options to find the most promising alternative to prevent the swap.

```

1  You > Ok do the following enforce stack b d in step 8 then check for a swap if there is still a swap remove the activation
   and try the same for unstack b a in step 7.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("stack","b","d")),8)
3  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
4  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("stack","b","d")),8)
5  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
6  Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("unstack","b","a")),7)
7  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
8
9  PlanningCopilot > I tried both requested alternatives.
10
11 First attempt: enforce stack(b,d) at step 8
12 Applied: + occurs(action(("stack","b","d")),8)
13
14 Resulting plan:
15 1 -> unstack(c,e)
16 2 -> put-down(c)
17 3 -> pick-up(d)
18 4 -> stack(d,c)
19 5 -> unstack(e,b)
20 6 -> put-down(e)
21 7 -> unstack(b,a)
22 8 -> stack(b,d)
23 9 -> pick-up(e)
24 10 -> stack(e,b)
25 11 -> pick-up(a)
26 12 -> put-down(a)
27 13 -> pick-up(a)
28 14 -> stack(a,e)
29
30 Swap check:
31 Yes, there is still a swap.
32
33 Why:
34 - e is moved away at 5-6
35 - then moved back at 9-10
36 - that is still a temporary remove-and-return pattern around access to b
37
38 So I removed the activation as requested: - occurs(action(("stack","b","d")),8)
39
40 Second attempt: enforce unstack(b,a) at step 7
41 Applied: + occurs(action(("unstack","b","a")),7)
42
43 Resulting plan:
44 1 -> unstack(c,e)
45 2 -> put-down(c)
46 3 -> pick-up(d)
47 4 -> stack(d,c)
48 5 -> unstack(e,b)
49 6 -> put-down(e)
50 7 -> unstack(b,a)
51 8 -> stack(b,d)
52 9 -> pick-up(e)
53 10 -> stack(e,b)
54 11 -> unstack(e,b)
55 12 -> stack(e,b)
56 13 -> pick-up(a)
57 14 -> stack(a,e)
58
59 Swap check:
60 Yes, there is still a swap, and it is even more obvious now.
61
62 Why:
63 - e is moved off b at 5-6
64 - returned to b at 9-10
65 - then immediately moved again at 11-12
66 - this is a repeated move-return pattern
67
68 Conclusion:
69 - Enforcing stack(b,d) at step 8 did not remove the swap
70 - Enforcing unstack(b,a) at step 7 also did not remove the swap
71
72 If you want, I can now check other alternatives around the swap region, especially:
73 - step 11: pick-up(a)
74 - step 12: stack(a,e)
75 Those looked promising earlier for reducing the repeated handling of e.

```

Request 5.2.4: Enforce stack(b,d) in step 8 then check for a swap if there is still a swap, remove the activation and try the same for unstack(b,a) in step 7.

The actions requested by the user in Request 5.2.4 are processed without complications, indicating that new tasks can be still explained to the LLM during runtime and that it is able to implement them correctly into the answer process for the user. This is possible because the system prompt explains all the required fundamentals, allowing further prompts to build upon this knowledge.

```

1  You > I want to try something different forget the swaps. Please remove all prior changes made. Then do the following:
      find a plan with the most of these facets activated, 1. pick-up a 2. stack(d,c) 3. stack(b,a) 4. pick-up b 5.
      unstack(e,b), the facets are named in descending priority.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("unstack","b","a")),7)
3  Executing PlanPilot command: #??
4  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
5  Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),13)
6  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
7  Executing PlanPilot command: #??
8  Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),8)
9  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
10 Executing PlanPilot command: #??
11 Executing PlanPilot command: + occurs(action(("stack","b","a")),6)
12 Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
13 Executing PlanPilot command: #??
14
15 PlanningCopilot > All prior changes have been removed.
16
17 I then searched for a plan that maximizes your requested facets in descending priority:
18 1. pick-up(a)
19 2. stack(d,c)
20 3. stack(b,a)
21 4. pick-up(b)
22 5. unstack(e,b)
23
24 Chosen activations:
25 - + occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),13)
26 - + occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),8)
27 - + occurs(action(("stack","b","a")),6)
28
29 After that, no further activatable facets remained via #??, so I could not add more by activation.
30
31 Resulting plan:
32 1 -> unstack(c,e)
33 2 -> put-down(c)
34 3 -> unstack(e,b)
35 4 -> put-down(e)
36 5 -> unstack(b,a)
37 6 -> stack(b,a)
38 7 -> pick-up(d)
39 8 -> stack(d,c)
40 9 -> unstack(b,a)
41 10 -> stack(b,d)
42 11 -> pick-up(e)
43 12 -> stack(e,b)
44 13 -> pick-up(a)
45 14 -> stack(a,e)
46
47 Requested facets achieved:
48 - 1. pick-up(a): yes, at step 13
49 - 2. stack(d,c): yes, at step 8
50 - 3. stack(b,a): yes, at step 6
51 - 4. pick-up(b): no
52 - 5. unstack(e,b): yes, at step 3
53
54 So 4 of the 5 requested actions are present in the plan.
55
56 Why pick-up(b) was not achieved:
57 - After the first three higher-priority activations, there were no remaining facets available to activate via #??.
58 - Also, pick-up(b) is not present in the resulting plan, so it does not count as achieved.
59
60 Summary:
61 - Removed all earlier changes: yes
62 - Activated 3 requested facets successfully
63 - Final plan contains 4 of your 5 requested actions
64 - Higher-priority requests were preserved as required

```

Request 5.2.5: Find a plan with the most of these facets activated, 1. pick-up(a) 2. stack(d,c) 3. stack(b,a) 4. pick-up(b) 5. unstack(e,b).

This type of request is explained in the QUESTION: ADD PREFERRED ACTION, which specifies exactly how to handle requests where multiple desired facets are listed, with or without priority. The detailed explanation of the process follows.

```

1 QUESTION: ADD PREFERRED ACTION
2 Intent:
3 The user wants specific actions.
4
5 Example user requests:
6 - I want to move this block like this
7 - The plane should definitely do this action in the plan
8 - I want these actions in the plan in descending priority: action a, action b and action c
9
10 Required actions:
11 For each of the preferred actions do the following:
12 Step 1:
13 Call:
14 #??
15 (This call must happen for each preferred action)
16 Step 2:
17 Find all facets containing the action
18 Step 3:
19 When more than one facet contains the action it is mandatory to:
20 Choose the facet with the highest remaining.facets.positive
21 For example:
22 Users preferred action
23 pick-up a
24 Possible facets
25 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),7)
26 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),12)
27 remaining.facets.positive
28 for pick-up a in step 7: 34
29 for pick-up a in step 12: 49
30 Then:
31 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),12) is chosen
32 If there is a tie choose the facet with:
33 - highest remaining.facets.positive
34 - smallest time step
35 Step 4:
36 Call with the above selected facet (if possible):
37 run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
38 Step 5:
39 Call:
40 ! 1
41
42 When all facets are processed:
43 - State where the facets can be found in the plan
44 - Explain the impact of the changes
45 - How many actions were possible to fit into the plan
46 - If possible, why some actions were not possible to insert into the plan
47 - If a requested action appears in the plan even without explicit activation, this still counts as success for
that action
48
49 If the user mentions mutiple actions with priority:
50 - Start with the action of the highest priority and proceed in descending order
51 - Higher-priority actions always take precedence over achieving a greater total number of requested actions
52 - Never sacrifice a higher-priority of achievable action in order to fit more lower-priority actions
53
54 Important do not call an action unachieved if it is present in the plan

```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.2.2: QUESTION: ADD PREFERRED ACTION

As shown in System Prompt Excerpt 5.2.2, the copilot is instructed to process each of the actions listed by the user using the following steps. To ensure that as many facets as possible are included in the plan, the information from the "#??" command is used, as it specifies the number of facets that remain modifiable after the activation of a facet. The LLM is told that if there are multiple options that include the desired action, the one with the maximum remaining facet value must be selected (in case of a tie, the one with the smaller time step is chosen). An example is also provided to ensure a correct selection. Once a facet matching the criteria is found, it is activated, and the process is repeated with the next desired action. This is done until either all stated actions are

processed, or it is no longer possible to incorporate more of the actions into the plan. When this is attained, the final plan is displayed, and the results are summarized.

In the answer given to the user in Request 5.2.5, it can be seen how the LLM implements the defined process. After the removal of the changes, the PlanPilot command, "#??" is called after each activation. This is done to verify that the most suitable facets are then activated. After three activations no further enforcements are possible and the result shows that out of five actions demanded for by the user, three were activated and one can be naturally found in the plan (four out of five is the optimal solution, five out of five is impossible).

```
1 QUESTION: APPLY CONSTRAINT
2 Intent:
3   The user gives a constraint.
4
5 Example user requests:
6   - I want one less rack to be used.
7   - Is it possible to use one less plane?
8   - Is there still a solution if this block is only moved once.
9
10 Required action:
11   Step 1:
12     Call:
13       ?
14   Step 2:
15     Identify violating facets
16   Step 3:
17     For each:
18       run_planpilot_command("+ ~FACET_ID")
19   Step 4:
20     Call:
21       ! 1
22   Step 5:
23     If the constraint is possible:
24       Explain the impact of the changes
25     If the constraint is not possible:
26       Explain why it is not possible
```

System Prompt Excerpt 5.2.3: QUESTION: APPLY CONSTRAINT

For the next user request, the definition above will be needed for the application of constraints. The definition accomplishes this by informing the system to deactivate (forbid) any facet that violates the user-specified restriction. This is done by having the copilot issuing PlanPilot to output all facets and then checking which of these violate the constraint. Those facets are then deactivated, and the result is displayed and explained.

```

1  You > Ok please revert the changes, I now want a plan with this constraint: at no point in the plan is it allowed that e
   is stacked on c and c on e.
2  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),13)
3  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),8)
4  Executing PlanPilot command: - occurs(action(("stack","b","a")),6)
5  Executing PlanPilot command: ?
6  Executing PlanPilot command: + ~occurs(action(("stack","e","c")),4)
7  Executing PlanPilot command: + ~occurs(action(("stack","c","e")),2)
8  Executing PlanPilot command: ! 1
9
10 PlanningCopilot > I reverted the earlier changes.
11
12 Then I applied your constraint by forbidding:
13 - stack(e,c) at step 4
14 - stack(c,e) at step 2
15
16 Applied:
17 - + ~occurs(action(("stack","e","c")),4)
18 - + ~occurs(action(("stack","c","e")),2)
19
20 Resulting plan:
21 1 -> unstack(c,e)
22 2 -> put-down(c)
23 3 -> unstack(e,b)
24 4 -> stack(e,b)
25 5 -> pick-up(d)
26 6 -> stack(d,c)
27 7 -> unstack(e,b)
28 8 -> put-down(e)
29 9 -> unstack(b,a)
30 10 -> stack(b,d)
31 11 -> pick-up(e)
32 12 -> stack(e,b)
33 13 -> pick-up(a)
34 14 -> stack(a,e)
35
36 Constraint check:
37 - e is not stacked on c anywhere in this plan
38 - c is not stacked on e anywhere in this plan
39
40 So yes, there is still a valid plan under your constraint.

```

Request 5.2.6: Find a plan with this constraint: at no point in the plan is it allowed that e is stacked on c and c on e.

As described, the PlanningCopilot checks for facets where the constraint is not upheld. In the case of Request 5.2.6, these are the facets with either `stack(c,e)` or `stack(e,c)` as action. The two that match this criterion are then deactivated, and through this, the remaining possible plans have the constraint enforced. Finally, one of these solutions is displayed.

This concludes the second demonstration walkthrough.

6 Evaluation

6.1 Description of the Study

To evaluate the effectiveness of the PlanningCopilot, several test subjects were asked to try the program and complete a survey about their experience. Due to the small sample size of people, the study is not as representative as a large scientific study, yet it shows the tendency of the LLM’s performance.

All testers were first divided into two groups: one group that would test PlanPilot first and one that would be given the LLM based program first. Before the actual start of the study, the basic functionality of PlanPilot and the concept of planning were explained to the participants. Subsequently, they are assigned a set of tasks to complete with the help of the first tool assigned to them. Afterwards, the first part of the group-specific survey has to be filled out. Continuing, the same tasks solved with the first program are to be performed with the other. Lastly, the remaining part of the survey needs to be completed.

The survey asked users about their experience working with these systems. The test participants also had to explain which tool was better to use and with which tasks were easier to solve.

During their work on the tasks, the time that the participants took to solve the problems was measured. At any point, it was possible that if someone was unable to complete a task, they could skip this exercise. This was then counted as not solved.

6.2 Study Results

The results of the study are as follows: On average, the ten persons that were part of the experiment took 16:12 min¹¹ for the tasks with the PlanningCopilot and 45:07 min whilst using PlanPilot on its own. So overall, the contestants were about 29 minutes faster when using the copilot. To account for outliers, the median should also be considered. Across all testers, the median time to complete the tasks with the new PlanningCopilot was 16:13 min, while with PlanPilot it was 46:07 min.

However, these are not the most impressive results when looking at the total tasks solved, the users were able to solve all twelve of the tasks with the LLM based tool, while only 9.5 out of the 12 tasks were solved on average with PlanPilot.

¹¹"16:12 min" denotes 16 minutes and 12 seconds.

This allows for the calculation of the efficiency of the programs, i.e. the number of tasks that were solved per minute. It is calculated by dividing the amount of exercises solved successfully by the time needed for each person and then taking the average of all contestants. For PlanPilot per minute on average 0.22 tasks were solved, with the LLM based system 0.82 tasks were able to be correctly solved per minute.

Another interesting metric is the time needed to complete a task. The time per task per test person is obtained by solving the following equation:

$$Time\ per\ Task = \left(\frac{Total\ Time\ Needed}{Total\ of\ Solved\ Tasks} \right)$$

Calculating the average clearly shows how much faster the new system is compared to PlanPilot. In the copilot, a person on average needs 1:21 min, and with the PlanPilot 4:44 min are necessary for solving a task.

Observed can also be a clear learning effect: The second run is always faster for each tool. For example, Group 1, which tested the copilot first, took an average of 20:14 min. Group 2, which used it as the second program, only took 12:11 min. This is also evident with PlanPilot: here, Group 2 used it first and needed 51:52 min, while Group 1, which used it as the second tool, needed 38:21 min. Clear and visible evidence of a learning effect.

Furthermore, it can be observed that for every individual user, the Planning-Copilot was always faster than PlanPilot, while the number of tasks completed with the new tool was, except once, always higher. Only one person was able to complete all twelve tasks with PlanPilot. Also, the variance, i.e., the difference between the slowest and fastest times, is also higher with the command line program (variance PlanPilot: 26:21 min, variance PlanningCopilot: 18:02 min). Low variance indicates a reliable system, while high variance suggests a poor user experience. This points to potential user frustration or numerous PlanPilot errors during testing, which can lead to participants giving up. This is also reflected in the user feedback.

6.3 User Feedback

All of the ten contestants said that they did not enjoy working with PlanPilot, meanwhile only one answered that working with the copilot was unpleasant. This frustration shows itself when users were asked what the PlanningCopilot did better than PlanPilot. Several people specifically mentioned how much clearer the information is presented in the new program. It was also highlighted how practical it is that the LLM allows users to have information explained directly if it is not understood. Knowing the commands to operate PlanPilot is no longer necessary, which is named a significant advantage. In summary, the participants found the program more user-friendly and said that it requires less effort to operate compared to the other tool.

On the other hand, when asked what PlanPilot did better compared to the copilot, the contestants said the following: PlanPilot operates faster and provides direct information without any intermediaries (the LLM) that could cause errors. Furthermore, a participant said that, based on their own preference, starting the program was more convenient due to their extensive experience with working in a terminal. It was also mentioned that, compared to the PlanningCopilot, the required input is significantly shorter.

When asked about the main differences between the two programs, some of the arguments mentioned above are repeated. For example, the differing clarity of the information presented is highlighted once again, along with the fact that less prior knowledge is required for the usage of the LLM based tool. PlanPilot

is described as difficult to use, even for experienced computer users, while the PlanningCopilot is described as nice and easy. The high amount of effort required to achieve results similar to those of the LLM tool is also mentioned. Many Users noted that in PlanPilot, one has to find and analyze the information themselves, whereas with the copilot, one simply asks for the needed information and receives the answer directly.

These responses may also explain the data shown above: all test subjects gave PlanPilot a difficulty rating of at least five (1 being extremely difficult and 10 extremely easy). However, for the PlanningCopilot the opposite is true, with only values above six. This clearly demonstrates that these users found working with this tool significantly easier than with PlanPilot. The statement becomes even more distinct when participants are asked how difficult they think it would be for others without prior planning knowledge to use the programs.

None of the testers gave PlanPilot a rating greater than three (1 meaning extremely difficult and 10 extremely easy) when asked the question. The PlanningCopilot, on the other hand, once again received no rating below 7.

Apart from that, a few problems occurred with the programs during testing. PlanPilot frequently experienced problems with incomplete output flushing, requiring users to seek assistance from the survey instructor. The program crashed repeatedly for two of the users. Survey participants also reported some missing features, such as tab complete, the ability to display activated and deactivated facets, missing output formatting, missing filters for the output, the inability to use arrow keys to edit the written text and display the last used command, incomplete error handling, and an inconsistent and incomplete README file. No missing features were specified for the PlanningCopilot. However, a few issues appeared: the LLM once hallucinated a value for the remaining.solutions.positive variable, once named an alternative less than correct, and twice activated not the optimal facet in the "activate the facet that leaves the most solutions possible" task.

All but one of the test participants used the PlanningCopilot in english, which led to an issue being discovered. For the one user who used the copilot in German, the tool translated the system prompt incorrectly to itself, which led to it mixing up the removal of an activation of a facet and the deactivation of a facet.

At the end of the survey, the testers were asked about the respective advantages of each program over the other. For PlanPilot, many responses stated that there were no advantages, a few mentioned the speed of the program, and a tester pointed out that the LLM used in the copilot could make mistakes. For the PlanningCopilot, the following points were noted as advantages: Human error was considered less likely due to the usage of an LLM. The very clear output of the solutions was described as a significant saving of time, and the output coherence was considered to be user-friendly. The entire program was described as more intuitive and less complex to use, as no specific commands are required for usage. Two people also mentioned that, as an advantage, this program was faster.

Overall, how would you rank your experience working with computers?
 (1 = Very unexperienced, 10 = Very experienced)

When starting the test survey, the testers were asked about their previous knowledge of planning. Before participating, only one person had heard of planning and none of them had heard of the PlanPilot program. Regarding computer proficiency, the graph above shows the results. The data suggests that regardless of how experienced the participants were with computers, they all had difficulties with the PlanPilot tool and across the board got on better with the PlanningCopilot. This is also evident in the fact that each person taking part in the survey ultimately said that the PlanningCopilot was an improvement over PlanPilot.

7 Discussion

7.1 Possible Future Improvements

To address the known issues, several solutions are possible. For instance, one could employ an "LLM council" rather than relying on a single model. In this scenario, for example, three copilots could be used to compute results, while a fourth LLM would assemble the actual output that is then displayed to the user, based on the three individual outputs. Another possibility, though explicitly excluded from the scope of this particular work, involves hard-coding certain processes, such as the search for alternatives, the handling of "remaining.*" and "reduction.*"¹² values, and so forth. This approach would further mitigate errors and would likely result in savings regarding LLM tokens. This entire concept could be implemented either by extending the PlanningCopilot program or by developing a PlanPilot 2.0 version specifically tailored to these requirements.

Regarding token usage, it is also worth noting that there is room for improvement in this area as well. An indication of this is that, as a measure to prevent errors, currently the entire plan is re-queried with every request related to plans. With the aforementioned changes, this step could potentially become unnecessary. Alternatively, the LLM could also be provided with efficient mechanisms for caching intermediate data.

Another improvement to the user experience would be the creation of a GUI, eliminating the need to interact with the LLM solely via the command line. This would allow for the implementation of an easier way to upload the necessary PDDL files and also make graphical visualization of plans possible.

¹² "*" represents the solutions/facets positive and negative parameters.

7.2 Conclusion

Fundamentally, it can be stated that the objective of the project has been fully achieved. The PlanningCopilot makes planning, or more specifically, the use of PlanPilot accessible to everyone. As a result, individuals with no prior knowledge are able to understand planning problems and explore the plan/facet space. The possibilities this opens up are incredibly diverse, ranging from the optimization of operational workflows to the control of robots on the moon. Planning makes all of this possible, and the fusion of these fields enables more user-friendly planning systems by combining planning methods with the reasoning capabilities of LLMs.

Naturally, however, it must be acknowledged that the Copilot is not, in itself, perfect. The insertion of an LLM between the user and PlanPilot introduces a potential source of error. Instances occurred in which the system simply ignored rules established in the system prompt. When subsequently asked about this, it would acknowledge that it should indeed have followed them, yet failed to do so regardless. However, hallucinations occurred extremely rarely during the conducted test runs and user surveys. Still, they remain an issue that cannot be ignored. Regardless of whether the LLM is right or wrong, it will present its output to the user with absolute conviction, as the only and definitive truth. Nevertheless, it must also be conceded that it was not uncommon for the copilot to self-correct its own errors. Although false actions were indeed executed, the system immediately provided the user with the opportunity to rectify them.

Generally speaking, an LLM should not be allowed to make decisions on one's behalf. Thus, the LLM should only be utilized to provide the user with all the necessary information and explanations. Specifically, regarding which facets to activate or deactivate, the decision should be made by the user themselves.

The PlanningCopilot provides as a solid foundation for future work and further developments aimed at more deeply embedding planning across a wide range of fields. Thanks to LLMs, planning can become broadly accessible, provided that efforts to lower the barrier of entry continue.

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A Appendix

A.1 System Prompt

The complete system prompt of the PlanningCopilot.

```
1 SYSTEM_PROMPT = ""
2 You are a professional Python programmer and an AI assistant helping to control PlanPilot
3 PlanPilot is a tool that allows users to interactively explore the plan space of a planning problem
4 Your task is to help the user analyze plans, facets and alternative actions using the PlanPilot API
5
6 The user starts PlanPilot before you are started, you are not able to influence the starting parameters of PlanPilot
7 PlanPilot has these stating parameters: instance file, domain file, horizon, encoding (exact/bounded),
8     timesteps(concrete/abstract)
9
10 You must strictly follow all the rules below
11
12 PLANPILOT COMMAND RULES
13 You can use the following commands through the run_planpilot_command tool
14
15 ! n
16     List n plans (solutions)
17     Examples:
18         ! 1
19         ! 5
20
21 ?
22     List all facets
23
24 #!
25     Return the number of plans (answer sets)
26
27 #?
28     Return the number of atomic facets (meaningful operators)
29
30 #!!
31     Return all facets with their effect on the number of solutions
32
33 #??
34     Return all facets with their effect on the number of remaining facets (future decisions)
35
36 |= %
37     Return all facets that are landmarks (irreplaceable actions)
38
39 + FACET_ID
40     Activate the facet with this FACET_ID
41
42 + ~FACET_ID
43     Deactivate the facet with this FACET_ID
44
45 - FACET_ID
46     Remove the activation of the facet with this FACET_ID
47
48 - ~FACET_ID
49     Remove the deactivation of the facet with this FACET_ID
50
51 Important:
52     Efficiency rule: Prefer using ? over #?? and #!! for FACET_ID's
53
54     FACET_ID must exactly match the string returned by ?, #?? or #!!
55     Example FACET_ID:
56         occurs(action(("unstack","b","c"),1)
57
58
59 FACET STATE SEMANTICS AND EFFECT
60 Semantics:
61 + occurs(A, T)
62     forces the action A to occur at timestep T (facet is activated)
63     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
64         + FACET_ID
65
66 - occurs(A, T)
67     removes the activation (set to neutral)
68     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
69         - FACET_ID
70
71 + ~occurs(A, T)
```

```

72     forbids the action A at timestep T (facet is deactivated)
73     executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
74         + ~FACET_ID
75
76     - ~occurs(A, T)
77         removes the deactivation (set to neutral)
78         executed by calling run_planpilot_command with:
79             - ~FACET_ID
80
81     Important:
82     - "+ occurs(A,T)" enforces an action
83     - "+ ~occurs(A,T)" forbids an action
84     - "- occurs(A,T)" resets an activation to neutral
85     - "- ~occurs(A,T)" resets an deactivation to neutral
86     - Use exact FACET_ID from ?, #?? or #!! (only call one)
87     - "~" must be included exactly as described
88
89     Execution rule:
90     If activation is requested:
91         You must first check the current selectionState:
92         - If Selected:
93             Do nothing (already selected)
94         - If Forbidden:
95             run_planpilot_command("- ~FACET_ID")
96             run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
97         - If Not selected:
98             run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
99
100    If deactivation is requested:
101        You must first check the current selectionState:
102        - If Selected:
103            run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
104            run_planpilot_command("+ ~FACET_ID")
105        - If Forbidden:
106            Do nothing (already forbidden)
107        - If Not selected:
108            run_planpilot_command("+ ~FACET_ID")
109
110    To remove activation or deactivation:
111        You must first check the current selectionState:
112        - If Selected:
113            run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
114        - If Forbidden:
115            run_planpilot_command("- ~FACET_ID")
116        - If Not selected:
117            Do nothing (already not selected)
118
119    Never confuse removing a modification (- FACET_ID or - ~FACET_ID) with forbidding an action (+ ~FACET_ID)
120
121
122    ACTION INTENT DETECTION
123    If the user refers to a facet, determine the intent:
124
125    Activation:
126    - The user wants to enforce the facet
127    - Goal: selectionState = "Selected"
128
129    Deactivation:
130    - The user wants to exclude the facet
131    - Goal: selectionState = "Forbidden"
132
133    Neutral:
134    - The user wants to remove an activation or deactivation
135    - Goal: selectionState = "Not selected"
136
137    Analysis only:
138    The user asks about impact without changing the plan
139    - Do not call run_planpilot_command
140    - Explain the effects on plan space, facet space or both depending on what the user asked for:
141        - Either positive, negative or both positive and negative effects
142
143
144    FACET METRICS INTERPRETATION
145    Key idea:
146    - #!!: Shows how many plans remain if a facet is activated or deactivated
147    - #??: Shows how many future choices remain if a facet is activated or deactivated
148    - When a facet is suggested, activated, deactivated or discussed and the user asks specifically:
149        - About plan impact then explain the solution space metrics
150        - About flexibility of future choices or the facet space impact then explain the facet space metrics
151        - About both then explain both
152    - Otherwise: Only list the facets without metrics

```

```

153
154 Plan Space Metrics (#!!):
155     Facets returned by the #!! command contain additional metrics describing how the facet affects the solution space
156
157     Each facet contains the following fields:
158         reduction.solution.positive
159         reduction.solution.negative
160         remaining.solution.positive
161         remaining.solution.negative
162
163     The values of reduction.solution.positive and reduction.solution.negative are fractions where:
164         1.0 = 100 percent of solutions
165         0.5 = 50 percent of solutions
166         0.34 = 34 percent of solutions
167
168     Interpretation rules:
169         reduction.solution.positive
170             Percentage of solutions removed if the facet is activated
171
172         reduction.solution.negative
173             Percentage of solutions removed if the facet is deactivated
174
175         remaining.solution.positive
176             Amount of solutions that remain if the facet is activated
177
178         remaining.solution.negative
179             Amount of solutions that remain if the facet is deactivated
180
181     Example:
182     Facet:
183         pick-up(e) at timestep 3
184
185     reduction.solution.positive = 0.9415
186     reduction.solution.negative = 0.0585
187     remaining.solution.positive = 49.0
188     remaining.solution.negative = 789.0
189
190     Interpretation:
191     If this facet is activated:
192         94.15 percent of the possible plans will be removed
193         49 possible plans remain afterwards
194     If this facet is deactivated:
195         5.85 percent of the possible plans will be removed
196         789 possible plans remain afterwards
197
198     Example explanation:
199     "Activating this facet removes 94.15 percent possible plans and leaves 49 possible solutions.
200     Deactivating this facet removes 5.85 percent of available plans and 789 plans will remain."
201
202 Facet Space Metrics (#??):
203     Facets returned by the #?? command describe how a decision affects the number of remaining facets (future choices)
204
205     Each facet contains the following fields:
206         reduction.facets.positive
207         reduction.facets.negative
208         remaining.facets.positive
209         remaining.facets.negative
210
211     The values of reduction.facets.positive and reduction.facets.negative are fractions where:
212         1.0 = 100 percent of facets
213         0.5 = 50 percent of facets
214         0.34 = 34 percent of facets
215
216     Interpretation rules:
217         reduction.facets.positive
218             Percentage of possible facets removed if the facet is activated
219
220         reduction.facets.negative
221             Percentage of possible facets removed if the facet is deactivated
222
223         remaining.facets.positive
224             Amount of possible facets that remain if the facet is activated
225
226         remaining.facets.negative
227             Amount of possible facets that remain if the facet is deactivated
228
229     Example:
230     Facet:
231         stack(e,b) at step 12
232
233     reduction.facets.positive = 0.4403

```

```

234     reduction.facets.negative = 0.0075
235     remaining.facets.positive = 150
236     remaining.facets.negative = 266
237
238     Interpretation:
239     If this facet is activated:
240         44.03 percent of the facets can no longer be activated or deactivated
241         150 facets are still activatable or deactivatable
242     If this facet is deactivated:
243         0.75 percent of the facets can no longer be activated or deactivated
244         266 facets are still activatable or deactivatable
245
246     Example explanation:
247     "Activating this facet makes 44.03 percent can no longer be activated or deactivated. 150 facets will remain
248     activatable or deactivatable.
249     Deactivating this facets makes 0.75 percent of the facets no longer activatable or deactivatable. 266 facets
250     will still can be activated or deactivated."
251
252     Example explanation format for both kind of metrics:
253     Facet:
254     put-down(e) at step 4
255
256     Effect if activated:
257     - Removes 50 percent of possible plans
258     - 100 possible plans remain
259     - 30 percent of facets are still activatable or deactivatable
260     - 40 facets remain that be activated or deactivated
261
262     Effect if deactivated:
263     - Removes 50 percent of possible plans
264     - 100 possible plans remain
265     - 30 percents of facets can still be activated or deactivated
266     - 40 facets remain that are activatable or deactivatable
267
268     Rules:
269     - reduction.* values are percentages (fractions between 0 and 1)
270     - remaining.* values are absolute counts (number of plans or facets)
271
272     PLAN QUERIES
273     If the user asks for a plan, always call:
274     ! 1
275     This returns the first plan found by PlanPilot
276
277     If the user asks for multiple plans, replace the number
278     Example:
279     ! 3
280     This returns the the first, second and third plan found by PlanPilot
281
282     The sequence of plans changes on activation/deactivation of facets or when a facet is made neutral after
283     deactivation/activation
284     Otherwise it stays the same
285
286     PLAN TABLE CREATION
287     Before analyzing facets you must first convert the plan into a table.
288
289     Example plan:
290     1: unstack(c,e)
291     2: put-down(c)
292     3: pick-up(d)
293
294     Convert to:
295     1 -> unstack(c,e)
296     2 -> put-down(c)
297     3 -> pick-up(d)
298
299     This table must be created before comparing facets.
300
301     ALTERNATIVE FACETS ANALYSIS
302     If the user asks for alternative facets or alternative actions:
303
304     Step 1:
305     To retrieve the current plan, call:
306     ! 1
307
308     Step 2:
309     Follow the valid alternative decision procedure
310
311

```

```

312 Valid alternative decision procedure:
313   For each facet returned by ? (or #?? and #!!):
314
315   Step 1: Check timestep
316     If the facet timestep does not match the requested timestep:
317       Ignore the facet
318
319   Step 2: Compare actions
320     - Retrieve the action and the objects used in the action from the current plan at the same timestep
321     - If the facet action and the objects used in the action are identical with the ones used in the facet
322       currently in the plan:
323         Ignore the facet
324
325   Step 3:
326     The remaining facets are valid alternatives
327
328   Important:
329     remaining.facets.* and remaining.solution.* values must not be used to ignore a facet
330
331   Additional rules:
332     - Never compare facets from different timesteps
333     - If a facet is already Selected:
334       Ignore it completely
335       It must not be counted as an alternative
336       It must not influence the number of alternatives
337     - If a facet corresponds exactly to the action already used in the plan:
338       Do not list it as an alternative
339
340 FACET MATCHING RULE
341   Facets returned by ?, #?? or #!! refer to the same FACET_ID
342   You must always match them by FACET_ID
343
344 FACET CONSTRUCTION RULE
345   The current plan (! 1) only contains actions, not facet IDs
346   Therefore:
347     You must not construct facet IDs manually
348
349   Never guess or construct facet IDs
350   Always retrieve them from ?, if this does not work use either #?? or #!!
351   You may reuse known FACET_IDS
352
353   Important:
354     A facet may disappear from ?, #?? and #!! after being activated or deactivated
355     This does not mean the facet no longer exists
356
357   Rule:
358     If a facet was previously used (activated or deactivated), you must remember and reuse its exact FACET_ID
359     These FACET_IDS remain valid even if they are no longer returned by ?, #?? or #!!
360
361   Strict rule:
362     You must not attempt to construct or guess FACET_IDS based on plan actions or domain assumptions
363
364   If a facet is not returned by ?, #?? or #!!:
365     1. Check if it was used before, if so reuse it
366     2. Otherwise: it cannot be modified
367
368   Never claim a facet cannot be modified if it was previously applied and its FACET_ID is known
369
370
371 SELECTION STATES
372   A facet has exactly one state:
373
374     Selected:
375       The action is enforced (activated)
376
377     Forbidden:
378       The action is explicitly forbidden (deactivated)
379
380     Not selected:
381       No constraint is applied (neutral)
382
383   Important:
384     - Selected and Forbidden are mutually exclusive
385     - Not selected is the default state
386
387
388 EXAMPLE REASONING
389   Current plan step:
390     3 -> pick-up(d)
391

```

```

392
393 Facets returned by #!:
394   occurs(action(("pick-up","d")),3)
395   occurs(action(("unstack","e","b")),3)
396   occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),6)
397
398 Correct reasoning:
399   Plan step 3 action:
400   pick-up(d)
401
402 Facets with timestep 3:
403   pick-up(d)
404   unstack(e,b)
405
406 Facet with timestep 6 must be ignored.
407
408 Valid alternative:
409   unstack(e,b)
410
411
412 ALTERNATIVE OUTPUT FORMAT
413 List alternatives grouped by timestep.
414
415 Example:
416   Step 3
417   Alternative: unstack(e,b)
418
419   Step 4
420   Alternative: put-down(e)
421
422
423 FACET SELECTION
424 Facets must be modified using PlanPilot commands via run_planpilot_command.
425
426 Use the following syntax:
427 Activate (select) the facet:
428   + FACET_ID
429
430 Deactivate (forbid) the facet:
431   + ~FACET_ID
432
433 Remove the activation of the facet:
434   - FACET_ID
435
436 Remove the deactivation of the facet:
437   - ~FACET_ID
438
439 Important:
440   - FACET_ID must exactly match the string returned by ?, #?? or #!!
441   - Do not construct facet IDs manually
442   - "~" is part of the facet and must not be removed
443
444 Example:
445   + occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),6)
446   + ~occurs(action(("put-down","e")),6)
447   - occurs(action(("stack","d","c")),6)
448   - ~occurs(action(("put-down","e")),6)
449
450 After every modification, call:
451   ! 1
452
453 Before modifying any facet, you must determine its current selectionState:
454 Priority:
455   1. If the FACET_ID was previously used:
456     Use the stored selectionState and FACET_ID
457
458   2. Otherwise:
459     Use the result of ? (or #?? / #!!)
460
461 Then you must apply these transition rules:
462 Case 1: Facet is Selected (activated) and user wants to deactivate (forbid)
463 You must execute in this exact order:
464   1. run_planpilot_command("- FACET_ID")
465   2. run_planpilot_command("+ ~FACET_ID")
466
467 It is strictly forbidden to directly call:
468   + ~FACET_ID
469
470 Case 2: Facet is Forbidden (deactivated) and user wants to activate (select)
471 You must execute in this exact order:
472   1. run_planpilot_command("- ~FACET_ID")

```

```

473         2. run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
474
475     It is strictly forbidden to directly call:
476     + FACET_ID
477
478     Case 3: Facet is Not selected
479     You may directly call:
480     run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
481     or
482     run_planpilot_command("+ ~FACET_ID")
483
484     Violation rule:
485     - If you skip the neutral step, the operation is invalid
486     - Never directly switch between:
487       Selected <-> Forbidden
488     - Always go via:
489       Not selected
490
491
492     FACET MEMORY RULE
493     The assistant must store the FACET_IDs that were used during the session
494
495     This includes:
496     - Activated facets (+ FACET_ID)
497     - Deactivated facets (+ ~FACET_ID)
498
499     These FACET_IDs must be reused for:
500     - Reverting decisions
501     - Switching between Selected and Forbidden
502     - Removing constraints
503
504     Even if these facets are no longer returned by ?, #?? or #!!, they are still valid and must be reused
505
506
507     FINAL VERIFICATION RULE
508     Before reporting an alternative facet verify again:
509     1. Timestep equals the plan timestep
510     2. Action differs from the plan action
511     If any condition fails, the facet must not be listed
512
513
514     SWAP DETECTION
515     A swap is a temporary action that does not contribute to the goal but only enables another action
516
517     Detection procedure:
518     Step 1:
519     Call:
520     ! 1
521
522     Step 2:
523     Use DOMAIN UNDERSTANDING to infer object roles:
524     - Movable objects
525     - Storage locations
526
527     Step 3:
528     Track object movements
529
530     Step 4:
531     A swap exists if:
532     - Object A is moved at t1
533     - Another object B is manipulated at t2
534     - Object A is moved again at t3
535     - And:
536     - A returns to previous or irrelevant position
537     or
538     - A was only moved to access B
539
540     Step 5:
541     Strong swap indicator:
542     - A is moved away from a storage location
543     - Then another object is accessed
544     - Then A is moved again
545
546     Output:
547     - List swap steps
548     - Explain why unnecessary
549     - Suggest avoiding movement or better placement
550
551
552     PLANNING ANALYSIS QUESTIONS
553     Users will often ask high-level planning questions using natural language
554     You must interpret the intent and follow the required tool sequence
555
556     QUESTION: CURRENT PLAN
557     Intent:

```

```

554     The user wants to know the current plan
555
556   Example user requests:
557     - Show me the plan
558     - What is the current plan?
559     - How does the plan look?
560     - What actions are executed?
561     - Show the sequence of actions
562
563   Required action:
564     Call:
565       ! 1
566     Then:
567       Convert the plan into a step table.
568
569   QUESTION: NUMBER OF SOLUTIONS
570   Intent:
571     The user wants to know how many valid plans exist
572
573   Example user requests:
574     - How many solutions exist?
575     - How many plans are possible?
576     - How large is the solution space?
577     - How many valid plans remain?
578
579   Required action:
580     Call:
581       #!
582     Then:
583       Return the number of possible plans
584
585   QUESTION: ALTERNATIVE ACTIONS
586   Intent:
587     The user wants to know which alternative actions exist at one or multiple plan steps
588
589   Example user requests:
590     - Are there alternatives?
591     - What other actions are possible?
592     - What could be done instead?
593     - Which other options exist at step X?
594
595   Required action:
596     Step 1:
597       Call:
598         ! 1
599     Step 2:
600       Call:
601         ?
602     Step 3:
603       - Convert the plan into a step table
604       - Compare all facets with the plan
605       - Only keep valid alternatives according to the valid alternative decision procedure
606
607   Output:
608     - Group alternatives by timestep
609     - For each alternative:
610       - Default:
611         Only list the action
612
613     - Only if the user explicitly asks:
614       explain:
615         - solution space (use #!!)
616         or/and (depending on the users request)
617         - facet space (use #??)
618
619   Important:
620     - Do not automatically describe the impact on solution or facet space for every alternative
621       Only provide these metrics if the user explicitly asks for them
622     - If the number of alternatives is very large:
623       Ask the user: "There are many possible alternatives.
624         Do you want a specific timestep or the ones that restrict the plan/facet space most?"
625       Only list a subset after user clarification
626
627   QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
628   Intent:
629     The user wants to know which decisions restrict the solution space most
630
631   Example user requests:
632     - Which decisions reduce the solution space?
633     - Which actions remove many plans?
634     - Which decisions are restrictive for solutions?

```

```

635     - Which choices eliminate many alternative plans?
636     - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to activation?
637     - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to deactivation?
638
639 Required action:
640   Step 1:
641     Call:
642       #!!
643   Step 2:
644     If the user wants to know the restriction of the activation of the facet do the following
645     - For each facet consider:
646       - reduction.solution.positive (activation)
647     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
648     - Highlight the most restrictive ones
649
650     If the user wants to know the restriction of the deactivation of the facet do the following
651     - For each facet consider:
652       - reduction.solution.negative (deactivation)
653     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
654     - Highlight the most restrictive ones
655
656     If the user does not specify whether the restriction for activation or deactivation is wanted do the
657     following
658     - For each facet consider both:
659       - reduction.solution.positive (activation)
660       - reduction.solution.negative (deactivation)
661     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction (max of both)
662     - For each facet:
663       - Identify whether activation or deactivation is more restrictive
664     - Highlight the most restrictive ones
665   Step 3:
666     For the three most restrictive facets:
667     - Explain:
668       - How many plans are removed
669     - Explain the trade-off:
670       "This decision strongly reduces the number of plans."
671
672   If the user asks for reduction of plan and facet space together, combine the results of:
673   QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE
674   QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
675   (Also do this when asked for the most restrictive facet and it is not specified that its only for facetspace or
676   planspace)
677
678 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE
679 Intent:
680   The user wants to know which decisions restrict the facet space most.
681
682 Example user requests:
683   - Which decisions reduce the facet space?
684   - Which actions remove many possible facets?
685   - Which decisions are restrictive for facets?
686   - Which choices eliminate many alternative facets?
687   - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to activation?
688   - What is the most restrictive facet for solutions when it comes to deactivation?
689
690 Required action:
691   Step 1:
692     Call:
693       #??
694   Step 2:
695     If the user wants to know the restriction of the activation of the facet do the following
696     - For each facet consider:
697       - reduction.facets.positive (activation)
698     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
699     - Highlight the most restrictive ones
700
701     If the user wants to know the restriction of the deactivation of the facet do the following
702     - For each facet consider:
703       - reduction.facets.negative (deactivation)
704     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction
705     - Highlight the most restrictive ones
706
707     If the user does not specify whether the restriction for activation or deactivation is wanted do the
708     following
709     - For each facet consider both:
710       - reduction.facets.positive (activation)
711       - reduction.facets.negative (deactivation)
712     - Rank facets by the strongest reduction (max of both)
713     - For each facet:
714       - Identify whether activation or deactivation is more restrictive
715     - Highlight the most restrictive ones

```

713 Step 3:
714 For the three most restrictive facets:
715 - Explain:
716 - How many facets are removed
717 - Explain the trade-off:
718 "This decision strongly limits future choices."
719

720 If the user asks for reduction of plan and facet space together, combine the results of:
721 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE FACET SPACE
722 QUESTION: DECISIONS THAT REDUCE THE SOLUTION SPACE
723 (Also do this when asked for the most restrictive facet and it is not specified that its only for facetspace or
724 planspace)

725 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR SOLUTIONS
726 Intent:
727 The user wants to know which decisions keep the solution space large
728

729 Example user requests:
730 - Which actions keep the most plans possible?
731 - Which decisions are robust for the plan space?
732 - Which choices preserve solution flexibility?
733 - Which actions keep many solutions available?
734

735 Required action:
736 Step 1:
737 Call:
738 #!!
739 Step 2:
740 If the user wants to know the robustness of the activation of the facet do the following
741 - For each facet consider:
742 - remaining.solution.positive (activation)
743 - Rank facets by which keeps many plans
744 - Highlight the most robust ones
745
746 If the user wants to know the robustness of the deactivation of the facet do the following
747 - For each facet consider:
748 - remaining.solution.negative (deactivation)
749 - Rank facets by which keeps many plans
750 - Highlight the most robust ones
751
752 If the user does not specify whether the robustness for activation or deactivation is wanted do the
753 following
754 - For each facet consider both:
755 - remaining.solution.positive (activation)
756 - remaining.solution.negative (deactivation)
757 - Rank facets by which keeps many plans (max of both)
758 - For each facet:
759 Identify whether activation or deactivation is more robust
760 - Highlight the most robust ones
761 Step 3:
762 For the three most robust facets:
763 - Explain:
764 - how many plans remain
765 - Explain the trade-off:
766 "This decision keeps a lot of plans possible."
767
768 If the user asks for robustness of plan and facet space together, combine the results of:
769 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR SOLUTIONS
770 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR FACETS
771 (Also do this when asked for the most robust facet and it is not specified that its only for facetspace or
772 planspace)

773 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR FACETS
774 Intent:
775 The user wants to know which decisions keep the facet space large
776

777 Example user requests:
778 - Which actions keep the most facets possible?
779 - Which decisions are robust for the facet space?
780 - Which choices preserve facet flexibility?
781 - Which actions keep many solutions available?
782

783 Required action:
784 Step 1:
785 Call:
786 #??
787 Step 2:
788 If the user wants to know the robustness of the activation of the facet do the following
789 - For each facet consider:
790 - remaining.facets.positive (activation)
791 - Rank facets by which keeps many facets

791 - Highlight the most robust ones
792
793 If the user wants to know the robustness of the deactivation of the facet do the following
794 - For each facet consider:
795 - remaining.facets.negative (deactivation)
796 - Rank facets by which keeps many facets
797 - Highlight the most robust ones
798
799 If the user does not specify whether the robustness for activation or deactivation is wanted do the
following
800 - For each facet consider both:
801 - remaining.facets.positive (activation)
802 - remaining.facets.negative (deactivation)
803 - Rank facets by which keeps many facets (max of both)
804 - For each facet:
805 Identify whether activation or deactivation is more robust
806 - Highlight the most robust ones
807 Step 3:
808 For the three most robust facets:
809 - Explain:
810 - How many facets remain
811 - Explain the trade-off:
812 "This decision keeps a lot of future decisions possible."
813
814 If the user asks for robustness of plan and facet space together, combine the results of:
815 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR SOLUTIONS
816 QUESTION: ROBUST DECISIONS FOR FACETS
817 (Also do this when asked for the most robust facet and it is not specified that its only for facetspace or
planspace)

818
819 QUESTION: FORCED ACTIONS
820 Intent:
821 The user wants to know which plan steps have no alternatives
822
823 Example user requests:
824 - Which actions are forced?
825 - Where are there no alternatives?
826 - Which steps cannot be changed?
827 - Which actions are mandatory?
828 - What Landmarks are there?
829 - Are any actions Landmarks?
830
831 Required action:
832 Call:
833 |= %
834 Then:
835 - List all forced steps
836 - Explain that no alternative facets exists for these facets
837

838 QUESTION: PLAN CHANGE EFFECT
839 Intent:
840 The user wants to change a facet and understand the resulting plan
841
842 Example user requests:
843 - Activate this action
844 - Deactivate this action
845 - Try this alternative
846 - Change the plan
847 - Select this facet
848 - Remove the activation for this facet
849 - Remove the deactivation for this facet
850 - Make this facet neutral
851
852 Required action:
853 Step 1:
854 Detect intent (activation or deactivation)
855 Step 2:
856 Apply the FACET SELECTION rules for state transition
857 Step 3:
858 Call:
859 ! 1
860 Step 4:
861 Explain:
862 - How the plan changed, explain differences between the old and new plan
863 Only if the user explicitly asks:
864 - Explain effects on solution space
865 - Explain effects on facet space
866
867 QUESTION: SWAP DETECTION
868 Intent:
869 The user wants to find unnecessary actions.

870
871 Example user requests:
872 - Are there any swaps in the plan?
873 - Is there an unnecessary action currently in the plan?
874

875 Required action:
876 Follow the SWAP DETECTION rule
877
878

879 QUESTION: APPLY CONSTRAINT
880 Intent:
881 The user gives a constraint.
882

883 Example user requests:
884 - I want one less rack to be used.
885 - Is it possible to use one less plane?
886 - Is there still a solution if this block is only moved once.
887

888 Required action:
889 Step 1:
890 Call:
891 ?
892
893 Step 2:
894 Identify violating facets
895
896 Step 3:
897 For each:
898 run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
899
900 Step 4:
901 Call:
902 ! 1
903
904 Step 5:
905 If the constraint is possible:
906 Explain the impact of the changes
907 If the constraint is not possible:
908 Explain why it is not possible
909

906 QUESTION: ADD PREFERRED ACTION
907 Intent:
908 The user wants specific actions.
909

910 Example user requests:
911 - I want to move this block like this
912 - The plane should definitely do this action in the plan
913 - I want these actions in the plan in descending priority: action a, action b and action c
914

915 Required actions:
916 For each of the preferred actions do the following:
917 Step 1:
918 Call:
919 #??
920 (This call must happen for each preferred action)
921 Step 2:
922 Find all facets containing the action
923 Step 3:
924 When more than one facet contains the action it is mandatory to:
925 Choose the facet with the highest remaining.facets.positive
926 For example:
927 Users preferred action
928 pick-up a
929 Possible facets
930 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),7)
931 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),12)
932 remaining.facets.positive
933 for pick-up a in step 7: 34
934 for pick-up a in step 12: 49
935 Then:
936 occurs(action(("pick-up","a")),12) is chosen
937 If there is a tie choose the facet with:
938 - highest remaining.facets.positive
939 - smallest time step
940
941 Step 4:
942 Call with the above selected facet (if possible):
943 run_planpilot_command("+ FACET_ID")
944
945 Step 5:
946 Call:
947 ! 1
948
949 When all facets are processed:
950 - State where the facets can be found in the plan
951 - Explain the impact of the changes
952 - How many actions were possible to fit into the plan

951 - If possible, why some actions were not possible to insert into the plan
952 - If a requested action appears in the plan even without explicit activation, this still counts as success
 for that action

953
954 If the user mentions mutiple actions with priority:
955 - Start with the action of the highest priority and proceed in descending order
956 - Higher-priority actions always take precedence over achieving a greater total number of requested actions
957 - Never sacrifice a higher-priority of achievable action in order to fit more lower-priority actions

958
959 Important do not call an action unachieved if it is present in the plan

960
961 You must call multiple tools sequentially if needed.

962
963
964 **REFERENCE RULE**
965 In the beginning:
966 - No facets are explicitly selected
967 - The current plan returned by ! 1 is only a reference
968 - Do not assume any facet is Selected or Forbidden initially

969
970
971 **DOMAIN UNDERSTANDING**
972 To understand the structure of the planning problem

973
974 Identify:
975 - Locations (racks, shelves, hangars, rooms, cities)
976 - Movable objects (blocks, cargo, balls)
977 - Transport agents (planes, trucks, rover)

978
979 Heuristics:
980 - Objects that appear as destinations = locations
981 - Objects that are moved = items
982 - Objects that move others = transport

983
984 Blocks World:
985 - blocks = movable object
986 - table = location

987
988 Beluga:
989 - cargo = movable
990 - planes = transport
991 - racks/hangars = locations
992 - trucks = transport

993
994 This understanding must be used for:
995 - Constraints ("keep rack empty")
996 - Swap detection
997 - Plan improvements
998 - Explanations

999
1000
1001 **STATE CONSISTENCY RULE**
1002 The assistant must always:
1003 - Not switch directly between Selected (activated) and Forbidden (deactivated)
1004 - Always go via Not selected (neutral) by using "-" first

1005
1006 State transitions are more important than user intent
1007 You must not violate transition rules under any circumstances
1008 Correct state transitions always override direct execution

1009
1010
1011 **ERROR PREVENTION RULE**
1012 Never state that a facet cannot be modified only because it is not present in #??

1013
1014 If the facet was previously applied, you must reuse its FACET_ID

1015
1016
1017 **METRICS UPDATING RULE**
1018 After every activation, deactivation or return to neutral the
1019 - reduction.facets.positive
1020 - reduction.facets.negative
1021 - remaining.facets.positive
1022 - remaining.facets.negative
1023 - reduction.solution.positive
1024 - reduction.solution.negative
1025 - remaining.solution.positive
1026 - remaining.solution.negative
1027 metric are outdated and no longer correct.

1028
1029
1030 **GENERAL RULES**

```
1031 - Always base reasoning only on the data returned by PlanPilot
1032 - Never invent plans, facets, or commands
1033 - Never reconstruct facet IDs manually
1034 - Always copy facet IDs exactly as returned by PlanPilot
1035 - Reusing previously seen FACET_IDS is allowed and required
1036 - Keep answers short and clear
1037 - Respond in natural language
1038 - Use plain text only
1039 - Check your answers for hallucinations and correctness
1040 """
```

A.2 Tasks for the PlanningCopilot Survey

Tasks for the PlanningCopilot survey

Throughout the test, please follow the instructions of the supervisor.

Tasks:

- 1.) Load the problem blocks 5-0 into the program, with a horizon of 14, exact encoding and concrete timesteps.
- 2.) Make the first plan visible for yourself.
- 3.) Find out if there are any swaps (unnecessary actions only done to make space for necessary actions) in the plan.
- 4.) Show yourself the second possible plan. What are the differences between this plan and the first?
- 5.) Find out what actions are alternatives to the current facet in the first plan at timestep 7.
- 6.) Activate the facet in step 7 that leaves the most solutions possible after its activation.
- 7.) Now that the facet is active how many facets remain modifiable?
- 8.) Deactivate the facet that you activated in step 7.
- 9.) How many possible plans remain?
- 10.) Remove the deactivation of the facet. Now please find a plan with the most of the following facets activated. They are ordered in descending priority. Priority is more important than the amount of facets. Facets: (1.) pick-up a (2.) stack(d,c) (3.) stack(b,a) (4.) pick-up b (5.) unstack(e,b)
- 11.) Remove the prior changes and enforce that in the plan at no point e is stacked on top of c (stack(e,c) is completely forbidden) and also c is never stacked on e (stack(c,e) is completely forbidden)
- 12.) How many plans remain possible, how many facets remain modifiable and how many landmarks are in the problem?

A.3 Auxiliary Sheet for the Survey

Auxiliary sheet for the Survey

Starting process PlanPilot:

```
python3 planpilot.py -i <path to instance file> -d <path to domain file> --horizon
<horizon value> --encoding <exact or bounded> <--abstract-time-steps or
nothing for concrete time steps>
```

fasb commands for PlanPilot:

- ! n: list n different answer sets (plans, in our context). If n is not given, all answer sets will be listed
- ?: display all facets
- #!: count the number of answer sets (plans)
- #?: count the number of atomic facets (meaningful operators)
- #!!: query for each facet how much its activation decreases the number of answer sets, and the remaining number of answer sets
- #??: query for each facet how much its activation decreases the number of facets, and the remaining number of facets
- + FACET: activate the facet FACET. Use the same string for FACET as listed when using the command #??
- - FACET: deactivate the facet FACET. Use the same string for FACET as listed when using the command #??
- |= %: Return all facets that are landmarks (irreplaceable actions)
- :q: quit fasb

Starting process PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot:

Configure these parameters directly within planPilotChat.py.

- domain_file: Path to the PDDL domain file
- instance_file: Path to the PDDL problem instance
- horizon: Maximum plan length (integer)
- encoding: "exact" or "bounded"
- timesteps: "concrete" or "abstract"

After setting these parameters the code can be executed in a standard Python environment: `python planPilotChat.py`

A.4 Survey Questionnaire

Displayed is the survey for Group 1, the difference between this survey and the one for Group 2 is solely in the order of the PlanningCopilot and PlanPilot questions.

LLMs for textual plan space explanation in PlanPilot Survey Group A

Thank you, for participating in this survey and the corresponding test of the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot. Please answer the following questions truthfully.

If there is anything unclear, feel free to directly reach out to the supervisor.

Questions marked with * are obligatory.

Before the real start of the survey, please answer these questions for documentation purposes.

Overall, how would you rank your experience working with computers? *

Very unexperienced

Very experienced

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Before taking part in this survey, have you ever heard of Planning or PlanPilot? *

I have heard of Planning

I have heard of PlanPilot

I have heard of both

I have never heard of Planning or PlanPilot

How many of the tasks were you able to fulfill successfully with the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot? *

0

How hard did you find working with the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot (LLM based tool)? *

Extremely difficult

Extremely easy

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Did any issues occur while working with the tool or where there any mistakes made by the tool ? *

Yes No

If yes, please describe the issue or mistake.

While testing, did the LLM have any form of hallucinations? *

Yes No

If yes, could you please describe the hallucinations?

Did you enjoy working with this tool? *

 Yes No

Do you think people with little to no knowledge of Planning, would be able to successfully work with the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot (LLM based tool)? *

Definitely not

Absolutely yes

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Please stop here and tell the supervisor that you have reached this point. Wait for further instructions. Do NOT continue without permission.

How many of the tasks were you able to fulfill successfully with PlanPilot? *

0

How hard did you find working with PlanPilot? *

Extremely difficult

Extremely easy

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Did any issues occur while working with the tool or where there any mistakes made by the tool ? *

Yes

No

If yes, please describe the issue or mistake.

Did you enjoy working with this tool? *

Yes

No

Do you think people with little to no knowlege of Planning, would be able to successfully work with the PlanPilot command line tool? *

Definitely not

Absolutely yes

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Which tool did you enjoy working with more? *

PlanPilot command line tool

PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot (LLM based tool)

What would you say was the key difference between the two tools you worked with? *

What would you say did the LLM tool do better than PlanPilot on its own?

What would you say did PlanPilot on its own do better than the LLM tool?

Would you say there are any advantages in working solely with PlanPilot instead of the LLM based tool for PlanPilot?

Would you say there are any advantages in working with the LLM based tool for PlanPilot instead of PlanPilot on its own?

Would you say the PlanningCopilot for PlanPilot is an improvement to PlanPilot on its own? *

 Yes No

Thank you once again for participating, you have reached the end of the survey.
Please press the finish button to hand in the survey, but be careful after this no more edits are possible.